

Master Thesis

Analysing nitrous oxide fluxes in a floodplain grassland in Lower Austria

submitted by

Silvia HEUFLER, BSc

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Supervisor

Assoc.Prof.Priv.Doiz.DI Dr.nat.techn. Johann Peter
Rauch
Institute of Soil Bioengineering and Landscape
Construction
Department of Landscape, Water and Infrastructure
University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences,
Vienna

Co-supervisors

Dipl.-Ing. Dipl.-Ing. Dr.techn. Bakk.techn.
Magdalena Von Der Thannen
Institute of Soil Bioengineering and Landscape
Construction
Department of Landscape, Water and Infrastructure
University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences,
Vienna

Anna Lindenberger BSc. MSc.
Institute of Soil Bioengineering and Landscape
Construction
Department of Landscape, Water and
Infrastructure
University of Natural Resources and Life
Sciences, Vienna

Affidavit

I hereby declare that I have authored this master thesis independently, and that I have not used any assistance other than that which is permitted. The work contained herein is my own except where explicitly stated otherwise. All ideas taken in wording or in basic content from unpublished sources or from published literature, as well as those which were generated using artificial intelligence tools, are duly identified and cited, and the precise references included.

I further declare that this master thesis has not been submitted, in whole or in part, in the same or a similar form, to any other educational institution as part of the requirements for an academic degree.

I hereby confirm that I am familiar with the standards of Scientific Integrity and with the guidelines of Good Scientific Practice, and that this work fully complies with these standards and guidelines.

Vienna, 01.04.2026

Silvia HEUFLER, BSc (*manu propria*)

This thesis is dedicated to Nonna Lydia, Oma Anna und Opa Max

“Nothing in life is to be feared; it is only to be understood. Now is the time to understand more, so that we may fear less.”

Marie Curie

Preface

The research presented in this master thesis was conducted in the framework of the project “REWET- REstoration of WETlands to minimise emissions and maximise carbon uptake” (grant number: 101056804), funded by the European Union and conducted at the Institute of Soil Bioengineering and Landscape Construction at the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna (BOKU) over the period March 2025 to December 2025, in cooperation with the environmental association WWF (World Wide Fund for Nature) Austria.

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Abstract

Nitrous oxide (N₂O) is a potent greenhouse gas (GHG) whose emissions are strongly influenced by hydrological and biogeochemical processes in wetland ecosystems. Floodplains play an important role in nitrogen (N) cycling and GHG regulation, yet the environmental controls governing N₂O dynamics in heterogeneous floodplain systems remain insufficiently understood.

This study was conducted within the framework of the EU project REWET and investigated N₂O fluxes in a floodplain grassland of the Morava River in the Marchauen Nature Reserve (Lower Austria). The objective was to quantify N₂O emissions under contrasting hydrological and land-management conditions and to evaluate the influence of soil temperature (soil_T), soil moisture (soil_M), and groundwater level (GW) on emission patterns in a grazed and a non-grazed transect.

N₂O fluxes were measured using the closed chamber method (CM) with a LI-COR trace gas analyzer. Environmental variables were continuously monitored using TOMST sensors and a piezometer, while soil samples were analysed to characterize physical and chemical soil properties. Statistical analyses included mutual information analysis (MI/RMI) and generalized additive models (GAM) to assess linear and non-linear environmental relationships.

The results revealed strong spatial and temporal variability in N₂O emissions and demonstrated that hydrological conditions represented the dominant environmental control. The wetter non-grazed transect showed consistently higher N₂O emissions, whereas the drier grazed transect exhibited lower and highly variable fluxes, including occasional N₂O uptake. Soil analyses further indicated that fine-textured, carbon (C) rich former channel structures promoted conditions favourable for denitrification and enhanced N₂O production.

Overall, the study demonstrates that N₂O emissions in floodplain ecosystems are governed primarily by hydrological conditions and associated oxygen availability rather than by grazing management alone. The findings highlight the importance of process-based understanding of local hydrological and biogeochemical interactions for wetland restoration and GHG mitigation strategies.

Kurzfassung

Lachgas (N_2O) ist ein hochwirksames Treibhausgas, dessen Emissionen stark durch hydrologische und biogeochemische Prozesse in Feuchtgebieten beeinflusst werden. Auenökosysteme übernehmen eine wichtige Rolle im Stickstoffkreislauf und in der Regulation von Treibhausgasen, jedoch sind die Umweltkontrollen von N_2O -Dynamiken in räumlich heterogenen Auenlandschaften bislang nur unzureichend verstanden.

Die vorliegende Arbeit wurde im Rahmen des EU-Projekts REWET durchgeführt und untersucht N_2O -Flüsse in einem Auenstandort der Marchauen in Niederösterreich entlang der March. Ziel der Arbeit war es, N_2O -Emissionen unter unterschiedlichen hydrologischen und landnutzungsbezogenen Bedingungen zu quantifizieren sowie den Einfluss von Bodentemperatur, Bodenfeuchte und Grundwasserdynamik in einem beweideten und einem unbeweideten Transekt zu analysieren.

Die Messung der N_2O -Flüsse erfolgte mittels geschlossener Chamber-Methode in Kombination mit einem LI-COR Trace Gas Analyzer. Umweltparameter wurden kontinuierlich mit TOMST-Sensoren und einem Piezometer erfasst, während Bodenproben zur Charakterisierung physikalischer und chemischer Bodeneigenschaften analysiert wurden. Zur statistischen Auswertung wurden Mutual Information Analysen (MI/RMI) sowie Generalized Additive Models (GAMs) eingesetzt, um lineare und nichtlineare Zusammenhänge zu untersuchen.

Die Ergebnisse zeigten eine starke räumliche und zeitliche Variabilität der N_2O -Emissionen und verdeutlichten, dass hydrologische Bedingungen den dominierenden Umweltfaktor darstellten. Das feuchtere unbeweidete Transekt wies durchgehend höhere N_2O -Emissionen auf, während das beweidete Transekt geringere und stark variable Flüsse zeigte, einschließlich zeitweiliger N_2O -Aufnahme. Die Bodenanalysen zeigten zudem, dass feinkörnige und kohlenstoffreiche ehemalige Gerinnestrukturen Bedingungen fördern, die Denitrifikation und damit die N_2O -Bildung begünstigen.

Insgesamt verdeutlicht die Studie, dass N_2O -Emissionen in Auenökosystemen primär durch hydrologische Bedingungen und die damit verbundene Sauerstoffverfügbarkeit gesteuert werden und weniger durch Beweidung allein. Die Ergebnisse unterstreichen die Bedeutung eines prozessbasierten Verständnisses hydrologischer und

biogeochemischer Wechselwirkungen für Feuchtgebietsrenaturierung und Treibhausgas-Minderungsstrategien.

1. Introduction

N₂O is a potent GHG with a global warming potential approximately 273 times higher than that of carbon dioxide (CO₂) over a 100-year time horizon and is currently the most significant ozone-depleting substance emitted in the 21st century (IPCC 2022). Anthropogenic activities, particularly agriculture and land-use change, have substantially altered the global N cycle, leading to increased N₂O emissions from terrestrial ecosystems (Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013; Galloway et al. 2008). Understanding the sources and controlling mechanisms of N₂O emissions is therefore critical for climate change mitigation and sustainable land management.

Floodplain ecosystems play a dual role in the global GHG balance. On the one hand, they act as important C sinks and contribute to biodiversity conservation. On the other hand, they can function as significant sources of GHG, including N₂O, depending on environmental conditions (IPCC 2022). The production and consumption of N₂O in soils are primarily governed by microbial processes such as nitrification and denitrification, which are highly sensitive to environmental factors (Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013).

In natural floodplain systems, hydrological dynamics are a key determinant of ecosystem functioning. Periodic flooding creates strong spatial and temporal variability in soil_M, oxygen availability, and nutrient distribution. These conditions directly influence microbial activity and thus regulate N₂O emissions (Welti 2012).

However, over the past century, many European river systems have undergone extensive hydromorphological alterations, including channelization, embankment construction, and drainage for agricultural use. These interventions have substantially altered natural hydrological regimes by modifying floodplain connectivity, GWT, and inundation dynamics. Such changes strongly affect soil_M conditions and associated biogeochemical processes, ultimately contributing to the ecological degradation of floodplain ecosystems as described under the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD 2000).

The Morava River floodplain in the Marchauen Nature Reserve represents a characteristic example of such a system (Figure 1). While still retaining elements of

near-natural floodplain dynamics, it has been influenced by historical regulation and land-use changes (WWF Österreich 2023).

Efforts are being made through EU projects such as LIFE+ „Renaturierung der Unteren March-Auen“ to remove infrastructure in order to create more natural areas, which are intended to improve water quality and the ecological footprint (Life+ 2026). Within the framework of the EU project REWET, this site provides an opportunity to investigate GHG fluxes under varying hydrological and management conditions (REWET 2025).

Figure 1: Regulation of the Morava River (WWF Österreich 2023)

Despite considerable progress in understanding N_2O emissions from soils, significant research gaps remain, particularly in heterogeneous environments such as floodplains. Previous studies have identified soil temperature (soil_T), soil_M, and groundwater table (GWT) as key controlling factors of N_2O fluxes. Soil_T regulates microbial activity, while soil_M and GWT control oxygen availability and thus the balance between aerobic and anaerobic processes. Peak N_2O emissions are often observed under intermediate moisture conditions, where both nitrification and denitrification can occur simultaneously. However, the interactions between these drivers are complex and often non-linear, and their combined effects remain insufficiently understood, especially under fluctuating hydrological conditions typical of floodplains (Pavelka et al. 2018; Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013; Kasak et al. 2022).

Furthermore, the influence of land management practices, such as grazing, on N_2O emissions in floodplain ecosystems is still not well quantified. Grazing can modify soil structure, compaction, vegetation composition, and nutrient inputs, thereby indirectly affecting microbial processes and gas flux dynamics (Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013). The

extent to which these effects interact with hydrological drivers represents a key knowledge gap.

Against this background, the present study aims to improve the understanding of N₂O emission dynamics in a floodplain ecosystem by investigating the role of key environmental drivers and land-use effects. The study addresses the following research questions:

1. How do environmental variables— soil_T, soil_M, and GWT —affect N₂O fluxes in floodplain soils?
2. How do N₂O fluxes and their relationships with environmental variables differ between grazed and non-grazed floodplain sites?

To answer these questions, a set of hypotheses was developed focusing on environmental controls of N₂O emissions and potential differences caused by land management.

1.1. Hypotheses

1.1.1. H1 - Environmental Controls of N₂O Fluxes

N₂O fluxes in floodplain soils are influenced by environmental conditions that regulate microbial N transformation processes such as nitrification and denitrification. In particular, soil_T, soil_M, and GWT are expected to influence the magnitude of N₂O emissions.

H1a₁: N₂O fluxes increase with increasing soil_T due to enhanced microbial activity.

H1b₁: N₂O fluxes show a non-linear relationship with soil_M, with higher emissions occurring at intermediate moisture levels where both nitrification and denitrification can occur.

H1c₁: N₂O fluxes increase with decreasing groundwater (GW) depth (i.e., a shallower GWT) due to increased denitrification activity under reduced oxygen conditions.

1.1.2. H2 – Influence of Land Management

To assess the potential influence of land use, N₂O emissions were compared between two sites with different management conditions: a grazed area (Transect A) and a non-grazed reference site (Transect B).

H2a₁: N₂O fluxes are higher in the grazed area (Transect A) due to manure deposition, soil disturbance, and vegetation changes caused by grazing.

H2b₁: The relationships between N₂O fluxes and environmental variables differ between the two transects due to differences in land management and soil conditions.

The hypotheses were tested using field measurements of N₂O fluxes combined with continuous monitoring of soil_T, soil_M, and GWT. Statistical analyses including correlation analysis, regression modelling, and non-linear modelling approaches were applied to evaluate the relationships between environmental variables and N₂O emissions.

Addressing these hypotheses contributes to a better understanding of N₂O emission dynamics in wetland ecosystems under different environmental and management conditions. Improved knowledge of these processes is essential for identifying GHG sources and sinks and for developing strategies to mitigate N₂O emissions in floodplain landscapes.

2. Theoretical Background

This chapter provides the scientific foundations necessary to understand the role of N₂O in floodplain ecosystems and its relevance for climate change. It describes the origin of this GHG, its behaviour in river–floodplain systems (Figure 2), and the influence of environmental conditions and human activities on its emissions.

2.1. The N Cycle in Soils

N is an essential nutrient for all living organisms and plays a central role in ecosystem functioning. In soils, N occurs in various organic and inorganic forms and is continuously transformed through a series of microbially mediated processes collectively referred to as the N cycle. These transformations regulate the availability of N for plant uptake and control the production and emission of reactive N gases, including N₂O (IPCC 2022).

The main processes of the soil N cycle include mineralization (ammonification), nitrification, denitrification, and immobilization. Mineralization converts organic N into ammonium (NH₄⁺), which can subsequently be oxidized to nitrate (NO₃⁻) through nitrification. Under oxygen-limited conditions, N can be reduced via denitrification to gaseous forms such as nitric oxide (NO), N₂O, and dinitrogen (N₂) (Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013). These processes are tightly coupled and strongly influenced by environmental conditions such as oxygen availability, temperature, and substrate supply.

Anthropogenic inputs, including mineral fertilizers, manure application, and atmospheric deposition, have substantially increased N availability in many ecosystems, thereby accelerating microbial N transformations and enhancing N₂O emissions. A major turning point in the global N cycle was the development of the Haber–Bosch process in the early 20th century. This industrial process converts atmospheric N₂ into ammonia (NH₃) under high temperature and pressure conditions and thereby produces synthetic N fertilizer on a large scale. The Haber–Bosch process dramatically increased the amount of reactive N available in terrestrial ecosystems and is considered one of the most important technological innovations in modern agriculture because it enabled substantial increases in crop productivity and global food production (Fowler et al. 2013). Today, anthropogenic N fixation through the Haber–

Bosch process equals or even exceeds natural terrestrial biological N fixation, fundamentally altering the global N cycle and increasing N losses to the environment, including nitrate leaching and N₂O emissions (Galloway et al. 2008; IPCC 2022; Fowler et al. 2013).

2.2. Microbial Pathways of N₂O Production

2.2.1. Nitrification

Nitrification is an aerobic microbial process in which NH₄⁺ is oxidized to NO₃⁻ via NO₂⁻. This process is primarily carried out by ammonia-oxidizing bacteria and archaea. Although nitrification mainly produces NO₃⁻, N₂O can be formed as a by-product, particularly under suboptimal oxygen conditions or when substrate availability is high (Equation 1).

Equation 1: Incomplete Nitrification under suboptimal oxygen conditions or high substrate availability

A related pathway, known as nitrifier denitrification, occurs when nitrifying microorganisms reduce N to N₂O under low-oxygen conditions (Equation 2). This pathway can contribute significantly to N₂O emissions in soils with fluctuating oxygen availability (Figure 2) (Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013).

Equation 2: Nitrifier denitrification under low oxygen conditions

2.2.2. Denitrification

Denitrification is the primary biological pathway for N₂O production in soils. It is an anaerobic process in which NO₃⁻ is sequentially reduced to NO₂⁻, NO, N₂O, and finally

N₂. This process is carried out by facultative anaerobic microorganisms that use N as an alternative electron acceptor in the absence of oxygen (Equation 3).

Equation 3: Complete Denitrification

The ratio of N₂O to N₂ produced during denitrification depends on environmental conditions. Incomplete denitrification, often caused by limited C availability or suboptimal redox conditions, results in increased N₂O emissions (Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013).

Equation 4: Incomplete denitrification under suboptimal redox conditions or limited substrate availability

2.2.3. Other Pathways

Additional pathways contributing to N₂O production include:

- Dissimilatory N reduction to NH₄⁺ (DNRA), which may indirectly influence N₂O formation
- Abiotic processes, such as chemical decomposition of N compounds under specific conditions

However, nitrification and denitrification are generally considered the dominant sources of N₂O in most terrestrial ecosystems (Butterbach-Bahl et al., 2013).

2.3. Environmental Controls of N₂O Emissions

The production and emission of N₂O are strongly regulated by environmental factors that influence microbial activity and substrate availability (Figure 2).

2.3.1. Soil_M and Oxygen Availability

Soil_M is one of the most important controls of N₂O emissions because it regulates oxygen diffusion in the soil. At low moisture levels, microbial activity is limited due to insufficient water availability. At high moisture levels, oxygen diffusion is restricted, leading to anaerobic conditions that favour denitrification (Pavelka et al. 2018; Welti 2012).

Maximum N₂O emissions are typically observed at intermediate soil_M levels, where both nitrification and denitrification can occur simultaneously (Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013).

2.3.2. Soil_T

Soil_T influences the rate of microbial processes by affecting enzyme activity and metabolic rates. Increasing temperature generally enhances both nitrification and denitrification, leading to higher N₂O emissions. However, the relationship is often non-linear, and extreme temperatures or freeze–thaw events can cause short-term emission peaks (Pavelka et al. 2018; Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013; Welti 2012).

2.3.3. GWT and Hydrology

In floodplain and wetland ecosystems, GWT is a key factor controlling soil redox conditions. Fluctuations in the GWT influence oxygen availability and create alternating aerobic and anaerobic conditions, which can stimulate N₂O production (Welti 2012).

Studies have shown that N₂O emission hotspots frequently occur when the GWT is close to the soil surface, as these conditions favour incomplete denitrification. Extremely high or low GWTs, however, may suppress N₂O emissions by either limiting microbial activity or promoting complete reduction to N₂ (Kasak et al. 2022).

2.3.4. Substrate Availability (N and C)

The availability of mineral N (NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻) and organic C strongly influences N₂O production. N provides the substrate for nitrification and denitrification, while organic C serves as an Energy source for denitrifying microorganisms (Welti 2012).

Limited C availability can inhibit the final step of denitrification, leading to increased N₂O emissions instead of complete reduction to N₂ (Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013; Kasak et al. 2022).

Figure 2: Conceptual representation of the N cycle in floodplain soils (Generated with Open AI 2026)

2.4. N₂O Emissions in Floodplain Ecosystems

Floodplains are characterized by strong spatial and temporal heterogeneity, driven by hydrological dynamics such as flooding, GWT fluctuations, and sediment deposition. These conditions create a mosaic of aerobic and anaerobic microsites, making floodplains hotspots of N transformation processes (Welti 2012).

Natural flood pulses enhance nutrient exchange between rivers and floodplains, promoting N retention and transformation. However, hydromorphological alterations, such as river regulation and floodplain disconnection, can significantly modify these

processes. Reduced flooding frequency and altered hydrology may lead to conditions that favour incomplete denitrification and increased N₂O emissions (Welti 2012).

Field measurements in Austrian floodplains have shown that N₂O fluxes typically range between 5 and 15 µg N₂O-N m⁻² h⁻¹, depending on hydrological conditions and site characteristics (Schindlbacher et al. 2022). These values highlight the importance of local environmental drivers and the need for site-specific investigations.

2.5. Conceptual Framework for This Study

This study assumes that N₂O fluxes in the Morava River floodplain are controlled by the interaction between hydrological conditions, soil properties, and land management. The conceptual framework assumes that spatial differences in groundwater influence and soil moisture create distinct redox environments that regulate microbial N transformation processes and consequently N₂O production and consumption.

Within the investigated floodplain, former channel structures and small-scale topographic depressions were expected to function as hydrologically active microsites with elevated soil moisture, reduced oxygen availability, and increased organic matter accumulation. Under such conditions, denitrification was expected to dominate over nitrification, potentially resulting in both elevated N₂O emissions and temporary N₂O sink behaviour depending on the degree of soil saturation and substrate availability.

The two investigated transects represent contrasting environmental settings within the floodplain. Transect A, located in a grazed area, was expected to be more strongly influenced by vegetation disturbance, localized nutrient inputs, and greater temporal variability in soil conditions. In contrast, Transect B was expected to exhibit more stable hydrological influence and wetter soil conditions due to its location within a non-grazed reference area with pronounced former channel structures. Based on these differences, spatial variability in the dominant environmental controls of N₂O fluxes was expected between the transects.

The study therefore assumes that N₂O dynamics cannot be explained by single environmental variables alone, but instead emerge from non-linear interactions between soil temperature, soil moisture, groundwater dynamics, and local soil

properties. This conceptual understanding formed the basis for the field measurements, statistical analyses, and hypotheses tested in this study.

3. Methodology

To address the research questions and test the formulated hypotheses, a methodological approach combining field measurements and statistical analysis was applied. The study design aims to quantify N₂O fluxes in a floodplain ecosystem while simultaneously monitoring key environmental variables that influence microbial N cycling processes.

This chapter describes the methodological framework and considerations underlying the implementation of the study. It begins with a description of the study site, followed by an overview of the hardware used for data collection and the software applied for data processing. Furthermore, the statistical analysis to answer the research questions are described. Detailed protocols, calculation procedures, and the code used for data processing and analysis are provided in the data set submitted along with this thesis.

3.1. Site description

The data collected for this thesis forms part of the EU-Project REWET to develop strategies for long term climate mitigation. In seven open labs around Europe (Figure 3) GHG such as N₂O, CO₂ and Methane (CH₄) are measured with the same methodology in peatlands/ floodplains/ freshwater wetlands to further understand the behaviour of GHG Fluxes in diverse areas (REWET 2025).

Figure 3: EU-REWET Project open laboratories location and wetland types (REWET 2025)

The study area is located in the Open Lab 2 (Figure 3) within the Floodplain Reserve Marchegg in Lower Austria, situated along the Morava River at the border between Austria and Slovakia. The reserve forms part of the larger March floodplain system (“Marchauen”), one of the most extensive near-natural floodplain landscapes remaining in Central Europe (Figure 4). Geographically, the site lies northeast of Vienna near the town of Marchegg and is included in the European Natura 2000 network due to its high ecological value (WWF Österreich 2023).

Figure 4: Overview of the Marchauen Nature Reserve (WWF Österreich 2023)

From a biogeographical perspective, the region belongs to the transition zone between the Central European and Pannonian climatic regions, with strong continental influence. The climate is typically classified as Pannonian, characterized by relatively low annual precipitation and high temperature amplitudes. Long-term climate data from the nearby Marchfeld region indicate mean annual temperatures of approximately 9–11 °C and annual precipitation sums ranging between 450 and 600 mm. Summers are generally warm to hot, frequently exceeding 25 °C, while winters are cold with regular frost periods. Precipitation shows a seasonal maximum during summer months, often associated with convective storm events, whereas spring periods are typically dry. This climatic setting promotes periodic drought conditions, which interact with flood dynamics to create highly variable soil_M regimes (ZAMG 2026).

Hydrologically, the floodplain is strongly influenced by fluctuations in river discharge and GWTs. Seasonal flooding events, although reduced compared to historical conditions due to river regulation, still play a key role in shaping ecosystem processes and sediment dynamics (Hein et al. 2004). The alternation between inundation and aeration phases leads to pronounced spatial and temporal heterogeneity in soil redox conditions, which is particularly relevant for biogeochemical cycling, including N transformations and GHG gas emissions (IPCC 2022).

The soils of the March floodplain are predominantly alluvial soils that reflect the dynamic depositional environment. According to the World Reference Base for Soil Resources (WRB), the dominant soil types are Fluvisols and Gleysols (FAO 2006). Fluvisols are characterized by their young age and weak horizon development, as they are formed from recent fluvial deposits consisting of alternating layers of sand, silt, and clay. This stratification reflects successive flood events and sedimentation processes. Due to their relatively high nutrient availability and variable texture, Fluvisols play a crucial role in floodplain productivity and biogeochemical cycling. In areas with a shallow GWT, Gleysols are common. These soils exhibit clear redoximorphic features, such as mottling and gleyic horizons, caused by periodic water saturation and oxygen depletion. Such conditions favour anaerobic microbial processes, including denitrification, making these soils particularly relevant for N₂O production and consumption. Locally, small-scale occurrences of organic-rich soils (e.g., humic or semi-terrestrial wetland soils) may develop in depressions with prolonged waterlogging, although true peat soils are limited in extent (Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013).

The chamber measurements (CM) and environmental variables have been measured in two different sites (transects) with overall fourteen points inside the Marchauen Nature Reserve. The first transect A consists of nine points aligned in a row close to the Open Lab of the BOKU and the REWET Project. The second transect B is located in a field approximately thirty walking minutes from transect A in a northwestern direction and consists of five points also aligned in a row. The points of each transect were selected to capture the greatest diversity of landscapes in the according area. Each point represents a ring firmly installed in the soil needed for the CM. In the following aerial image, a map overview of both transects is shown (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Map Overview Transect A and Transect B Morava River (March) and Castle Marchegg

Starting with point Mg_a1, located at a relatively high, mostly dry site, (close to the Eddy Covariance Tower of the Open Lab) the points gradually descend, with points Mg_a5 and Mg_a6 situated entirely within a now-dry former channel. Moving toward Mg_a9, the final point of transect A, the terrain rises again, placing it between the surrounding woodland and the old channel. The points are located with approximately three to five meters distance from one another. Throughout transect A, semi-wild Konik horses graze and live undisturbed. In the Open Lab the Piezometer has been installed. In the following aerial image transect A and the Piezometer are depicted (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Transect A (natural grazers area) with REWET Open Lab 2 and Piezometer

Throughout the measurement period the vegetation height has been estimated per ring to roughly capture the growth rate (Figure 7). None of the rings has been flooded during the observation timeframe.

Figure 7: Vegetation hight of transect A

In consultation with the reserve ranger, a second transect location was established, situated away from the horses. The main reasons for selecting this area were that it also features a dry, old channel, providing environmental conditions appearing similar to transect A, but without grazing horses (natural grassland mown twice a year).

It should be noted, however, that transect B is considerably shorter than transect A, consisting of only five points instead of nine. The first point, Mg_b1, is the highest and is situated near a tree. As the point numbers increase, they gradually approach the channel, with the final point, Mg_b5, located at the channel's lowest point. This area has never been subjected to such measurements. In the following aerial image transect B is illustrated (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Transect B (biennially mown area)

The same estimation of vegetation height has been made in transect B (Figure 9: Vegetation height of transect B Figure 9). Also, here the rings never where completely flooded. The last ring of the transect Mg_b5 was saturated with water until the 26 of May 2025 and fell dry in June without vegetation. The field has been mown on the 17 of June 2025. However, transect B was left out of the mowing as not to disturb the measurement rings.

Figure 9: Vegetation hight of transect B

3.1.1. Soil Samples

To obtain the detailed information on the soil properties of the study sites, several soil samples were collected along both transects and subsequently analysed at the laboratory of the Institute of Soil Research at BOKU. The laboratory analyses provided essential information on soil chemical and physical characteristics, including C and N contents as well as additional parameters relevant for understanding the environmental conditions of the research area. These data contribute to a more comprehensive interpretation of the measured GHG fluxes and site-specific soil processes.

Soil samples were collected at two different depths, namely 0–20 cm and 20–50 cm below the soil surface, in order to capture potential vertical variability in soil properties. Along transect A, three sampling locations were selected in proximity to the measurement rings A2, A6, and A8, whereas along transect B, two sampling locations were established near rings B1 and B4. At each location, samples were taken from both depth intervals, resulting in a total of ten soil samples (Figure 5).

The collected soil samples were analysed using standardized laboratory procedures to determine a range of physical and chemical soil properties. Soil texture (sand, silt, and clay fractions) was determined through particle-size analysis using the “Köhn pipette” method. Prior to analysis, organic matter was removed by oxidation with hydrogen

peroxide (H_2O_2), followed by chemical dispersion using sodium pyrophosphate (Müller et al. 2009).

The soil pH was measured electrometrically in a soil suspension with a soil-to-solution ratio of 1:2.5, typically using either calcium chloride (CaCl_2) or distilled water as the extraction medium. Electrical conductivity (elc) was determined in a soil–water extract, commonly prepared at a 1:5 soil-to-water ratio, providing an estimate of the soluble salt content of the soil. Plant-available phosphorus and potassium (P-CAL and K-CAL) were analysed using the calcium acetate lactate (CAL) extraction method according to VDLUFA (Association of German Agricultural Analytic and Research Institutes) guidelines. Phosphorus concentrations were determined photometrically using the molybdenum blue method, while potassium was quantified either by flame photometry or inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES). The concentrations of exchangeable cations (K, Na, Mg, and Ca) as well as the cation exchange capacity (CEC) were determined through extraction with 1 M NH_4^+ acetate (NH_4Ac , pH 7) or barium chloride (BaCl_2), following standardized VDLUFA procedures. The extracted cations were subsequently quantified using ICP-OES or atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS). The CEC was calculated either as the sum of exchangeable cations or determined via NH_4^+ exchange. Total C (C_{tot}), inorganic C (C_{inorg}), and organic C (C_{org}) contents were analysed using dry combustion with an elemental analyser (CNS). Total C was measured directly, while inorganic C was determined separately after acid treatment or calculated from carbonate measurements. Organic C was subsequently derived from the difference between total and inorganic C fractions. The total N content (N_{tot}) of the soil samples was determined simultaneously with C using the same CNS elemental analysis procedure. Based on these measurements, the C/N ratio was calculated from the values of organic C and N_{tot} , providing an important indicator of soil organic matter composition and nutrient dynamics (VDLUFA 2012).

3.2. Hardware and Software

N_2O fluxes were quantified using the CM in combination with a LI-COR trace gas analyzer. This approach represents an internationally established standard for measuring soil–atmosphere gas exchange GHG research (IPCC 2022). The CM enables

spatially explicit measurements directly at the soil surface and is particularly suitable for heterogeneous environments such as floodplains, where soil_M, vegetation cover, and hydrological conditions vary at small spatial scales. The LI-COR analyzer allows high-resolution, real-time detection of trace gas concentrations, ensuring reliable quantification of low N₂O fluxes (Pavelka et al. 2018).

The method is portable, non-destructive, and minimally invasive, making it well suited for application in protected ecosystems such as the Marchegg Nature Reserve. Repeated measurements facilitate the assessment of both baseline emissions and short-term flux dynamics, for example following flooding or freeze–thaw events (LI-COR 2025).

To evaluate the environmental controls of N₂O emissions, key soil and hydrological parameters were continuously monitored. Soil_T and soil_M were recorded using TOMST sensors, which provide high-frequency measurements at multiple depths and enable detailed temporal analysis of soil conditions (TOMST 2025). GWTs were measured using a piezometer, allowing continuous observation of water table fluctuations. This parameter is particularly relevant in floodplain systems, as GW depth strongly regulates soil oxygen availability and thereby influences microbial processes such as nitrification and denitrification (Kasak et al. 2022). In addition, atmospheric conditions were documented during each chamber measurement. A standardized protocol included the recording of measurement time, air temperature, and relative humidity, which were measured using sensors integrated within the chamber before and after each sampling event (Pavelka et al. 2018).

The CM system consists of three main components: a trace gas analyzer, a measurement chamber, and permanently installed soil rings or floating collars that define the measurement area. These components function as an integrated system for in situ quantification of gas fluxes between soil and atmosphere. The analyzer continuously measures gas concentrations and is connected to the chamber via an inlet and outlet tube, enabling air circulation during measurements. The chamber is placed onto pre-installed soil rings, which must form an airtight seal to ensure accurate flux calculations. To minimize disturbance effects, the rings were installed at least 24 hours prior to measurement, allowing soil conditions to stabilize. Immediate measurements

after installation may alter soil structure and lead to artificially elevated fluxes, thereby increasing uncertainty (Pavelka et al. 2018; LI-COR 2025).

The measurement chamber and rings used in this study were custom manufactured in Estonia in collaboration with the University of Tartu. The following subsections describe the individual hardware and software components in more detail. All the necessary equipment has been transported to the field with a beach buggy as shown in the following Figure 10.

Figure 10: Bringing the Equipment to the field

3.2.1. Chamber

The chamber is constructed from white polyvinyl chloride (PVC) and is precisely designed to fit onto the gutter of the measurement ring. The chamber has a bell-shaped geometry, with a height of 50 cm, a bottom diameter of 51 cm, and a top diameter of 41 cm. All joints are sealed with silicone to ensure an airtight structure and prevent unintended air exchange during measurements. A mini ventilator is mounted on the inner side of the chamber lid to ensure proper mixing of the air inside the chamber during the measurement period. The ventilator is powered by a power bank located outside the

chamber. Additionally, an air temperature and humidity sensor is installed on the inner side of the lid to monitor the environmental conditions inside the chamber before and after measurements (can be seen in the attached Protocols). In Figure 11 the inner part of the chamber is shown. The chamber lid is equipped with two hermetically sealed ports featuring push-button connectors. These connectors allow the attachment of the inlet and outlet tubes that connect the chamber to the trace gas analyzer. Through these tubes, air circulates from the chamber to the analyzer and back again. This configuration forms a closed measurement loop, ensuring that air pressure within the chamber remains stable throughout the measurement period. The following Figure 12 depicts the Chamber with the tubes (Pavelka et al. 2018; LI-COR 2025).

Figure 11: Inner part of the chamber with air temperature and humidity sensors and ventilation

Figure 12: Chamber placed on ring with tubes and power bank on top

3.2.2. Measurement points

At each measurement point a ring constructed from PVC and have a circular shape with a diameter of 51 cm was installed. The lower section of each ring, which is inserted into the soil, has a height of approximately 8 cm. The upper part of the ring is designed as a gutter, which must be filled with water to create an airtight seal when the chamber is placed on top.

The rings are installed directly into the soil using either manual pressure or a hammer, depending on soil resistance and field conditions. Once installed, they remain fixed in place for repeated measurements throughout the monitoring period. Figure 13 shows the installation of the rings in transect A.

Figure 13: Installation of the rings in Transect A

When the CM is applied on open water surfaces, a floating device (floating noodle) is used instead of a soil ring. The floating noodle is attached to the lower rim of the chamber and provides sufficient buoyancy to keep it stable on the water surface. For accurate measurements, it is essential that the lower rim of the chamber remains fully submerged, thereby forming a hermetic seal between the chamber and the water surface. Figure 15 illustrates the floating noodle installed inside the chamber and Figure 14 shows the chamber floating on the water surface during a measurement.

Figure 15: Floating noodle in Chamber

Figure 14: Chamber floating on water

3.2.3. LI-COR Trace Gas Analyzer

The gas measurements in the field were conducted using a trace gas analyzer manufactured by LI-COR Biosciences. The instrument measures N_2O concentrations in parts per billion (ppb) and water (H_2O) vapor in parts per million (ppm). Figure 16 illustrates the analyzer and its main components.

The analyzer is equipped with a wireless (Wi-Fi) connection, which allows the recorded data to be transmitted in real time to a mobile phone or computer used in the field. This functionality enables the operator to immediately monitor the measurement process and verify the quality of the recorded data. During operation, air from the chamber is continuously drawn into the analyzer through the inlet tube. Inside the device, gas concentrations are determined using optical absorption spectroscopy, where the number of gas molecules per unit of air is quantified based on the interaction of light with the gas sample. This method enables the determination of trace gas concentrations with high temporal resolution and precision. After passing through the analyzer, the air is returned to the chamber via the outlet tube. This closed-loop circulation system ensures that no significant pressure differences occur between the chamber and the surrounding environment during the measurement period. Maintaining stable pressure conditions is essential to avoid artificial changes in gas flux (LI-COR 2025).

Figure 16: LI-COR Trace Gas Analyzer (LI-COR 2025)

Each measurement is conducted over a five-minute period, during which the analyzer records one data point per second. To minimize potential disturbances caused by chamber placement and initial mixing effects, the first two minutes of data are excluded from further analysis. Consequently, each measurement point yields 180 valid data points, which are used to calculate the gas flux for the respective ring location (LI-COR 2025).

3.2.4. Software for LI-COR Trace Gas Measurements

The software used for operating and managing the gas flux measurements is the cloud-based platform “LI-COR Cloud”. This platform enables the centralized collection, management, and preliminary analysis of environmental measurement data obtained from connected instruments. Data recorded by the trace gas analyzer are automatically transmitted to the cloud system, allowing users to access the information in real time from any location without the need for additional software installations or local data storage. To access the platform in the field, a smartphone, tablet, or computer must first be connected to the Wi-Fi network of the trace gas analyzer. After establishing the connection, the user enters the device-specific IP address in a web browser. Once connected successfully, the LI-COR Cloud interface automatically opens in the browser and displays the current measurement session (Figure 17).

Figure 17: Interface LI-COR Cloud: 1) N_2O and H_2O snapshot 2) LI-COR Analyzer Status 3) Software Settings

The platform allows users to visualize, download, and share measurement data efficiently. In addition, it provides several integrated data management and analysis functions, including basic data visualization tools, automated quality control routines, gap-filling functions, and daily summaries of measured gas fluxes, such as N_2O and H_2O . Figure 18 illustrates an example of a real-time graph displaying N_2O concentrations recorded during field measurements. Overall, the software considerably simplifies data handling and supports efficient remote monitoring and preliminary evaluation of environmental measurements in field experiments (LI-COR 2025).

Figure 18: Interface LI-COR Cloud: 1) N₂O Flux Measurement, 2) Measuring Parameters, 3) Download Interface

3.2.5. TOMST

Figure 19: TOMST Data Logger (TOMST 2025)

To monitor soil_M and soil_T at the measurement sites, sensors manufactured by TOMST were installed. The TOMST (Time-Domain Reflectometry Soil-Moisture) sensor determines soil_M indirectly by measuring the number of high-frequency electromagnetic pulses (approximately 2.5 GHz) transmitted through its printed circuit board within a defined time interval. The measured pulse count is converted into a signal value that depends on the relative permittivity of the surrounding soil. Relative permittivity is strongly influenced by the soil_M; therefore, the sensor signal can be used to estimate soil_M (cm³ cm⁻³). Typical

signal values range from approximately 350 for dry air to 3650 for demineralised H₂O. After calibration against a gravimetric reference method, the sensor provides a rapid and non-destructive estimation of soil_M. In addition to soil_M measurements, the device records soil_T at three different depths, allowing continuous monitoring of thermal conditions within the soil profile (Figure 19). The sensors are connected to dedicated TOMST dataloggers that store the measurement data and allow later retrieval and processing. Data handling and calibration procedures are supported by the corresponding software (Section 2.2.6) (TOMST 2025; Wild et al. 2019).

The calibration of the TOMST sensor establishes a quantitative relationship between the raw sensor signal and the true volumetric soil_M (cm³ cm⁻³). Because the relationship between sensor signal and soil_M varies depending on soil texture and structure, calibration must be conducted separately for each soil type. In this study, the sensors were calibrated in the laboratory using soil samples collected from Transect A and Transect B, respectively. The calibration procedure followed the manufacturer's guidelines (Haase 2025) and consisted of the following steps:

Approximately 10 L of soil from the respective transect were collected, air-dried, and sieved through a 2 mm sieve to remove coarse fragments. The soil was then repacked into a calibrated container with a defined volume in order to determine the bulk density. The container volume was marked to ensure reproducible soil mass during each moisture step. A series of at least five (preferably seven or more) different moisture levels was generated. The amount of H₂O required for each step was calculated based on the soil porosity, which had been determined from undisturbed soil samples. H₂O was added incrementally, and the soil was mixed thoroughly after each addition to ensure a homogeneous distribution of moisture. A TOMST datalogger equipped with the sensor was inserted into the packed soil sample. The device recorded the sensor signal at 15-minute intervals. Measurements were continued until the signal stabilized for each moisture level, which typically required approximately ten consecutive readings (Haase 2025).

Figure 20: 1) Data logger in soil sample 2) Covered with food foil to prevent evaporation (Haase 2025)

For each moisture condition, a soil subsample was collected and weighed in its wet state. The sample was then dried at 60 °C and weighed again to determine the gravimetric soil water content. Using the known bulk density, the gravimetric moisture values were converted into soil_M. The paired values of sensor signal and soil_M were plotted and fitted with a regression model, typically a second-order polynomial. Extremely dry or saturated values were excluded if necessary. The resulting regression equation was subsequently used to convert future sensor signals into soil_M values (Haase 2025).

The results of the calibration procedure are presented in the Results chapter.

3.2.6. Software LOLLI

For the management and processing of data recorded by the TOMST dataloggers, the software LOLLI was used. This software environment enables users to download, visualize, and export measurement data after field deployment. To access the data stored on the datalogger, the device must be connected to a computer using a USB reader device (Figure 21), which allows communication between the datalogger and the software interface (Figure 22) (TOMST 2025; Wild et al. 2019).

Figure 21: Reading the datalogger through the USB device in the field

Temp 3 26.9°C
Serial: 94200888

Battery: 0%
Used memory: 0

Temp 2: 25.4°C
Mod: Basic

Temp 1: 27.3°C
Soil moisture count: 494

TMS: 06.09.2024 12:18:57 1)
PC Time: 06.09.2024 14:18:59
Delta: +00:00:00

TMS firmware: 1.82^00

Log Terminal

Save Clear Log all

A -3E-9 _B_ 0.000161192 _C_ -0.109956505

Id	Serial	datetime	t1	t2	t3	hum	water
▶ 1	94200888	2024.09.06 14:19:14	27.125	25.4375	27	496	0

You've already read this device !!!

Show data Read again

06.09.2024: Remain: 0 days Addr: 004C68;\$004C68/\$004C68 Local=14:18:57 UTC=12:18:57 (+GMT=1) speed: 826 evt/s

Figure 22: Interface LOLLY Software (TOMST 2025)

Within the LOLLI software environment, collected data can be quickly inspected using simple graphical visualizations, allowing an initial evaluation of measurement quality. The data can then be exported in CSV format, enabling further processing and statistical analysis using external software tools (Figure 23) (TOMST 2025; Wild et al. 2019).

Figure 23: LOLLY Software Export to CSV (TOMST 2025)

In addition to data visualization and export functions, the software includes built-in calibration tools that allow the conversion of raw sensor signals into soil_M values based on the previously established calibration relationships. Furthermore, LOLLI enables users to configure measurement intervals and update the firmware of the dataloggers if required (TOMST 2025; Wild et al. 2019).

3.2.7. Piezometer

To monitor GWT fluctuations during the measurement period, a piezometer was installed near the eddy covariance tower along Transect A (Figure 6). The piezometer enables the continuous observation of GW dynamics and provides additional environmental information that may influence GHG fluxes measured at the site.

For the installation, a borehole with a depth of approximately 1.5 m and a diameter of 15 cm was drilled manually. A perforated PVC pipe of the same diameter was then inserted

into the borehole. The pipe was wrapped with geotextile material along its sides and at the bottom in order to allow H₂O infiltration while preventing the entry of fine sediment particles. The pipe had a total length of 2 m, thereby extending slightly above the ground surface to allow safe access for sensor installation and maintenance (Figure 24).

Figure 24: Installed Piezometer near transect A

To measure pressure conditions inside the piezometer, two pressure sensors (HOBO water level data logger U20L) manufactured by HOBO were installed (Figure 25). One sensor was positioned above the H₂O table to measure atmospheric pressure, while a second sensor was installed below the H₂O table to record hydrostatic pressure within the GW column (LI-COR, 2025).

Figure 25: HOBO Water Level Data Logger (LI-COR 2025)

The GWT (cm) was subsequently calculated as the difference between the hydrostatic pressure recorded by the submerged sensor and the atmospheric pressure recorded by the upper sensor. This pressure difference was converted into H₂O column height to determine GW fluctuations over time (LI-COR 2025).

3.2.8. Software HOBO

The so called “HOBOware” is a software platform developed by Onset Computer Corporation for configuring, downloading, and analyzing data from HOBO data loggers. It supports both USB and optical data offloading and provides a streamlined workflow for device setup, data retrieval, and visualization. The software includes tools for graphing, scaling, and basic statistical analysis of environmental data, facilitating efficient interpretation of time-series measurements. It enables reliable handling and evaluation of high-resolution environmental monitoring data in field-based studies (Onset 2026).

3.2.9. Protocols

For each measurement day, a field protocol was maintained to document the procedure and relevant environmental conditions. The protocol recorded the exact time for each chamber measurement at both transects. In addition, air temperature and relative air humidity were documented before and after each measurement for every sampling point. The protocol also included notes on special circumstances or irregularities that occurred during the measurement day, such as weather changes, technical issues, or disturbances that could potentially influence the measurements. Maintaining these protocols ensured traceability and quality control throughout the data collection process. An example for such a protocol is provided in the Appendix. All protocols and calculations can be found in the data set submitted along with this thesis.

3.2.10. R 4.4.3.

For data processing, statistical analysis, and visualization, the software R Version 4.4.3 was used. RStudio is an integrated development environment (IDE) for the statistical programming language R, providing a comprehensive interface for writing code,

performing analyses, and visualizing data. The software is widely used in scientific research because it supports the processing of large datasets, reproducible workflows, and the integration of numerous open-source packages designed for specialized statistical analyses and graphical representations.

In this study, R 4.4.3 was used to clean, process, and analyse the collected measurement data, as well as to generate the graphical visualizations presented in the results section. Raw N₂O concentration data from the LI-COR trace gas analyzer were processed and converted into fluxes using custom scripts based on functions from the tidyverse. Data import from Excel files was performed using readxl, while data cleaning, transformation, and aggregation were carried out using dplyr. Date handling and string processing were supported by lubridate and stringr, respectively. To investigate relationships between N₂O fluxes and environmental variables, MI and RMI were calculated using the infotheo package, including permutation-based significance testing. In addition, GAMs were applied to assess potential non-linear relationships between N₂O fluxes, soil_T, and soil_M, using the mgcv package. Data visualization was performed using ggplot2, and multiple plots were combined into publication-quality figures using patchwork. Processed datasets and model outputs were exported using readr.

The platform therefore served as a reliable and efficient tool for quantitative data analysis and interpretation (R-4.4.3 2025). The following chapter describes the mathematical and statistical approaches implemented in R 4.4.3 to analyse and interpret the collected data. All R scripts used in this study are provided in the dataset that comes with this thesis, enabling full reproducibility of the analytical workflow.

3.3. Statistical Analysis

In this chapter the statistical frameworks are described to understand how the collected data has been processed to generate significant results.

3.3.1. Flux calculation

N₂O fluxes were quantified using a concentration-based approach derived from the temporal change in gas concentration within a closed chamber system. This method,

widely applied in soil–atmosphere exchange studies, determines the net exchange of N_2O between the soil surface and the chamber headspace from the rate of concentration change over time ($\Delta C/\Delta t$). This rate was converted into an area-based flux by scaling with the chamber volume-to-surface area ratio (V/A) and applying a temporal conversion factor to express fluxes on an hourly basis. To obtain physically meaningful and comparable units, measured N_2O concentrations, originally recorded in parts per billion (ppb), were converted into mass-based concentrations using a multi-step procedure. First, values were transformed into molar fractions, followed by application of the ideal gas law using standard atmospheric pressure (101300 Pa) and the universal gas constant. Concentrations were then converted to mass units using the molar mass of N_2O and finally expressed as $\text{N}_2\text{O}\text{-N}$ to align with standard reporting conventions in soil biogeochemistry. Temperature was incorporated in these calculations as a critical variable; chamber air temperature was determined as the mean of manually recorded values before and after each chamber measurement and converted from degrees Celsius to Kelvin (Pavelka et al. 2018; LI-COR 2025).

Flux estimation was based on linear regression of N_2O concentration against time, assuming linear concentration dynamics during the selected measurement interval. The slope of the regression represents $\Delta C/\Delta t$, while the adjusted coefficient of determination (adjusted R^2) was used as a quality control metric to assess the reliability of the fit. Low adjusted R^2 values may indicate non-linear concentration patterns, chamber disturbances, or measurement artifacts. To minimize such effects, only the stabilized phase of chamber closure was considered for analysis. Specifically, the initial period following chamber deployment—potentially affected by pressure fluctuations or incomplete gas mixing—was excluded, and only the final 180 seconds of each measurement were used for flux calculation (Douglas C. Montgomery 2012).

Data processing was conducted in R using a custom-built workflow (see dataset provided with the thesis). Raw measurement files obtained from the LI-COR 7820 gas analyzer were imported and consolidated into a structured dataset containing timestamps, chamber identifiers, environmental variables, and gas concentrations. During preprocessing, potentially biased measurements were manually identified based on timestamp criteria and relabelled to ensure traceability and enable exclusion or separate evaluation in subsequent analyses. In addition, an automated filtering

routine was implemented to remove implausible values and reduce noise in the dataset. Measurement-specific adjustments were applied where necessary to account for irregularities in individual time series.

$$PV = nRT \qquad N_2O \text{ (mg m}^{-3}\text{)} = \left(\frac{N_2O_{ppb}}{101300} \cdot \frac{1000 \times 10^6}{8,3143 \cdot T} \right) \cdot \frac{44.013}{28,0134}$$

$$N_2O \text{ Flux} = \frac{\Delta C}{\Delta t} \cdot \frac{V}{A} \cdot 3600 \qquad \text{Adjusted } R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

Equation 5: Calculation N2O Flux (from R Code)

For each chamber measurement, linear regression was applied to the selected time interval to derive $\Delta C/\Delta t$, which was subsequently used for flux calculation according to Equation 5. The resulting N₂O fluxes were expressed in units of mass per area per time, consistent with standard GHG reporting. Alongside the flux values, auxiliary parameters—including mean chamber temperature, number of observations used in the regression, and duration of the analyzed interval—were retained to facilitate quality assessment and interpretation of the results. Finally, all processed data, including calculated fluxes and associated metadata, were exported as comma-separated values (CSV) files to support subsequent statistical analysis and visualization (Pavelka et al. 2018; LI-COR 2025)

3.3.2. Mutual Information Theory: MI and RMI

To quantify the relationship between environmental drivers and N₂O fluxes, an information-theoretic approach based on MI was applied. MI quantifies the reduction in uncertainty of one variable given knowledge of another and is derived from entropy using joint and marginal probability distributions (Equation 6). Unlike classical correlation measures such as Pearson correlation, MI detects linear, non-linear, and non-

monotonic dependencies. It is always non-negative and equals zero only when variables are statistically independent (Cover und Thomas 2005; Sturtevant et al. 2016).

$$I(X; Y) = \sum_{x,y} p(x, y) \log \left(\frac{p(x, y)}{p(x) p(y)} \right)$$

Equation 6: Calculation MI (Cover und Thomas 2005)

This approach is particularly suitable for soil–atmosphere gas exchange systems, where N₂O production and consumption are controlled by complex and interacting drivers. For instance, soil_M effects are typically non-linear, with peak emissions under intermediate conditions and reduced fluxes under saturation due to complete denitrification to N₂. Additional interactions among soil_T, GWT, and substrate availability further contribute to system complexity (Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013). To enable comparison between predictors, RMI was calculated by normalizing MI with the entropy of the response variable (Equation 7):

$$RMI = \frac{MI}{H(Y)}$$

Equation 7: Calculation RMI (Cover und Thomas 2005)

Entropy $H(Y)$ describes the uncertainty or variability of N₂O flux and is defined as (Equation 8):

$$H(Y) = - \sum_y p(y) \log p(y)$$

Equation 8: Calculation Entropy (Cover und Thomas 2005)

where $p(y)$ is the probability of observing the value y . Higher entropy indicates greater variability and reaches its maximum when all outcomes are equally likely (Cover und Thomas 2005).

The analysis was performed separately for transect A and transect B. Data were imported from an Excel dataset containing LI-COR and TOMST measurements and restricted to N₂O flux, soil_M, soil_T, GWT, and the categorical variable REMARK. Date formats were standardized, numerical variables converted accordingly, and observations assigned to transects via pattern matching of REMARK. soil_M was harmonized to percentage units, and only finite numeric values were retained. As MI requires discrete inputs, all continuous variables were discretized using equal-frequency (quantile-based) binning to ensure balanced observation counts per bin and improve entropy estimation. The number of bins was determined dynamically based on sample size using the square-root rule and constrained between 4 and 20. Robustness was evaluated by testing alternative binning schemes using a shuffle surrogate approach, resulting in a final configuration that included an increased number of bins for soil_M in transect B to better capture variability under high moisture conditions (Cover und Thomas 2005; Sturtevant et al. 2016)

MI between N₂O flux and each predictor (soil_M, soil_T, GWT) was calculated using the function `mutinformation()` from the R package *infotheo*, while entropy was computed using `entropy()`. RMI values were subsequently derived for each predictor and transect, yielding comparable measures of dependency strength (R-4.4.3 2025).

Statistical significance was assessed using a shuffle surrogate (permutation) test. For each predictor–response pair, N₂O flux values were randomly permuted 999 times while preserving the predictor distribution, thereby generating a null distribution of MI values under the assumption of independence. The observed MI was compared against this distribution, with p-values calculated as the proportion of permuted values greater than or equal to the observed MI. A z-score was additionally computed to quantify deviation from the null expectation. Relationships were considered significant when the observed MI exceeded the 95th percentile of the surrogate distribution (Sturtevant et al. 2016).

Results were summarized in Table 3, presenting MI and RMI values for each predictor with transects A and B shown side-by-side. Statistical significance was indicated using

standard notation ($p < 0.05$, $*p < 0.01$, $**p < 0.001$). All derived metrics, including MI, RMI, p-values, and z-scores, were exported as tables for the results section. The complete R code used for the analysis is provided in the additional dataset that comes with this thesis (Sturtevant et al. 2016).

3.3.3. GAM

To analyse the relationships between environmental variables and N_2O fluxes, GAMs were selected as the main regression framework. GAMs extend generalized linear models by replacing fixed linear terms with smooth functions, thereby allowing complex, non-linear relationships between the response variable and the predictors to be estimated directly from the data. In the following Equation 9 Y is the response variable (N_2O flux), $g(\cdot)$ is the link function, β_0 is the intercept, and $f_i(X_i)$ are smooth functions describing the effect of each predictor variable X_i (Lai et al. 2024).

$$g(E(Y)) = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n f_i(X_i)$$

Equation 9: General GAM formulation (Lai et al. 2024)

In ecological and environmental studies, this flexibility is particularly advantageous because biogeochemical processes are rarely strictly linear and are often shaped by thresholds, asymptotic responses, and interacting controls. Formally, GAMs express the expected response as the sum of an intercept and smooth functions of the predictor variables, which are typically represented by spline-based terms (Equation 10). Model fitting is performed using penalized likelihood estimation, which optimizes the trade-off between goodness of fit and model smoothness and thereby reduces the risk of overfitting. The degree of non-linearity is indicated by the estimated degrees of freedom (edf), where values close to one suggest an approximately linear response and higher values indicate increasing non-linearity (Lai et al. 2024).

$$E(N_2O\ flux) = \beta_0 + f_1(soil_T) + f_2(soil_M) + f_3(GWT)$$

Equation 10: GAM formula for the thesis specific predictors (Lai et al. 2024)

In addition to estimating main effects, GAMs allow the inclusion of interaction surfaces between predictors, which is especially relevant for N₂O dynamics because soil_M, soil_T, and GW conditions may act jointly rather than independently (Equation 11). Statistical inference is based on approximate F-tests for the smooth terms, allowing the significance of each predictor and interaction to be evaluated. Because predictors in ecological datasets often exhibit concavity, that is, the non-linear analogue of collinearity, the interpretation of predictor importance can be obscured when explanatory power is shared among variables. To address this, the concept of average shared variance can be used to decompose overall model fit into individual contributions of each predictor, expressed as individual R² values that sum to the total adjusted R² or explained deviance. This provides a complementary measure of relative importance beyond conventional significance testing and improves the interpretation of GAM results in the presence of correlated environmental drivers (Lai et al. 2024).

$$E(N_2O\ flux) = \beta_0 + f_1(soil_T) + f_2(soil_M) + f_3(GWT) + f_{12}(soil_T,soil_M) + f_{13}(soil_T,GWT) + f_{23}(soil_M,GWT)$$

Equation 11: GAM formula including interactors (Lai et al. 2024)

The dataset was imported from the same Excel file as for the MI/ RMI Calculation and again processed using the statistical software R. All column names were standardized, and relevant variables were extracted, including N₂O flux, soil_T, soil_M, GWT, and a categorical identifier for each measurement point (REMARK). Only complete cases with finite numeric values for all variables were retained.

Separate GAMs were fitted for transect A and transect B to account for differences in environmental conditions and system behaviour between the two sites. The response variable was N₂O flux, while soil_T, soil_M, and GWT depth were included as predictor variables. The model structure included both main effects (predictors) and interaction

terms. The smooth terms $s()$ allow each predictor to influence N_2O flux in a non-linear manner, while the tensor interaction terms $ti()$ capture potential combined effects between predictors. Model fitting was performed using restricted maximum likelihood (REML), which provides stable and reliable estimates of smoothing parameters (Lai et al. 2024; R-4.4.3 2025).

To interpret the influence of each environmental variable, partial effects were extracted from the fitted GAMs. For this purpose, predictions were generated along a sequence of values for each predictor, while all other variables were held constant at their median values. This approach isolates the effect of a single predictor on N_2O flux while controlling for the influence of the remaining variables. Confidence intervals (95%) were calculated based on the standard error of the fitted values. These partial response curves provide a direct visualization of how N_2O flux responds to changes in individual environmental drivers. To examine the combined influence of environmental variables, interaction surfaces were generated for each pair of predictors. This was achieved by predicting N_2O flux across a two-dimensional grid spanning the observed range of both variables, while holding the third variable constant at its median value. The resulting surfaces were visualized using contour plots, allowing the identification of regions with enhanced or reduced N_2O emissions under specific combinations of environmental conditions. This approach enables a detailed assessment of whether interactions between variables amplify or dampen N_2O flux responses (Lai et al. 2024).

The significance of each smooth term and interaction was evaluated based on approximate F-tests provided by the GAM framework. P-values were used to determine whether individual predictors or interactions significantly contributed to explaining variation in N_2O fluxes. In addition, the proportion of deviance explained by each model was calculated as a measure of overall model performance. This metric indicates how well the model captures the variability in the observed data. To assess potential redundancy or dependency between predictors, concurvity diagnostics were calculated. Concurvity is the non-linear analogue of multicollinearity and indicates whether one predictor can be approximated by a combination of others, which may affect the interpretability of individual effects (Lai et al. 2024).

3.3.4. ARIMAX

The piezometer installed at the study site had a total installation depth of 1.5 m. During the observation period, however, GWTs dropped below the sensor due to unusually dry and warm conditions in the nature park. Consequently, the piezometer ran dry between 2 May 2025 and 23 June 2025, resulting in a gap in the GWT time series. To ensure a continuous dataset for further analysis, the missing values were reconstructed using data from external monitoring sources. GWT records from three nearby observation wells operated by the hydrographic service of the Lower Austrian Provincial Government (Hydrographischer Dienst des Amtes der NÖ Landesregierung) were used as predictor variables. The selected stations—304543 Baumgarten an der March, 331769 Baumgarten an der March, and 326520 Marchegg—provide continuous and reliable measurements near the study area (<https://ehyd.gv.at/>).

A multivariate regression-based approach was initially considered and preferred over classical geostatistical interpolation methods such as kriging or inverse distance weighting. This decision was based on the specific hydrogeological conditions of the study area. In particular, a flood protection levee separates the landscape into hydraulically distinct GW bodies, limiting the spatial comparability required for geostatistical methods. Furthermore, regression-based approaches allow the explicit incorporation of temporal dynamics, which is essential for capturing seasonal GW fluctuations, such as the typical decline in H₂O levels during summer (George E. P. Box, Gwilym M. Jenkins, Gregory C. Reinsel 2015). Following a comparative evaluation of different modelling approaches, the ARIMAX (Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average with Exogenous variables) model was identified as the most suitable method for reconstructing the missing GW data (Figure 26). ARIMAX extends the traditional ARIMA framework by incorporating external predictor variables, enabling the model to account for both temporal dependencies within the GW time series and influences from surrounding monitoring wells. The model consists of three main components: an autoregressive (AR) term, which relates current values to past observations; an integrated (I) term, which addresses non-stationarity through differencing; and a moving average (MA) term, which incorporates past forecast errors. By integrating exogenous variables, ARIMAX provides a robust framework for modelling complex environmental

time series and improving the accuracy of reconstructed GWTs (George E. P. Box, Gwilym M. Jenkins, Gregory C. Reinsel 2015).

The line graph compares measured and modeled groundwater levels from January to July using multiple data series in different colors, including HOB0 Regression, HOB0 ARMAX, and HOB0 measured, as well as two additional monitoring points and precipitation amounts shown as bars. Groundwater levels fluctuate between 135 and 142, while precipitation varies, with a noticeable decline in the HOB0 Regression trend toward July.

Figure 26: Comparison of measured and modelled GWTs

4. Results

In this chapter, the analysed soil samples are presented alongside the observed environmental and experimental outcomes. This includes the characterization of soil properties, as well as the measured N₂O fluxes, GWTs, soil_T dynamics, and soil_M conditions throughout the study period. Furthermore, the results of the applied statistical analyses are reported, providing insights into the effects of the investigated factors and their interactions. The outcomes of the different statistical models and methods are presented to support the interpretation of the observed patterns and processes.

4.1. Soil Samples

In the following Table 1 the results of the soil sampling can be seen. The location of the samples is shown in Figure 5, whereas the label A describes the samples taken in transect A and B the samples taken in transect B and the according number describes the ring number the sample has been extracted close to and the depth it has been taken out at. The presented Table 2/ table 1? summarizes the physical properties of the soil samples per analyzed Ring and Transect. It shows the percentage of Silt Clay and Sand of each sample location (VDLUFA 2012).

	<i>Sand</i>	<i>Silt</i>	<i>Clay</i>
A2	14,73	43,75	41,52
A6	4,05	50,50	45,45
A8	20,60	38,84	40,56
B1	26,37	33,17	40,46
B4	9,24	43,73	47,03

Table 1: Physical Properties of the soil samples

Table 2 shows the chemical properties of the analyzed soil samples across two depth intervals per analyzed location (0–20 cm and 20–50 cm). The chemical parameters include pH measured in a 0.01 M CaCl₂ solution, and elc expressed in $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$. P-CAL and K-CAL were determined using the CAL extraction method and are reported in mg kg^{-1} . Exchangeable base cations (K, Na, Mg, Ca) as well as the CEC are given in mmolc kg^{-1} . C and N fractions are expressed as percentages (%), including C_{tot}, inorganic carbon C_{inorg}, organic carbon C_{org}, and N_{tot}. There has not been found any C_{inorg} in any of the samples, which means that in this case C_{tot} equals C_{org}. The C/N ratios presented as a dimensionless indicator of organic matter quality. In general, higher concentrations of C and N were observed in the upper soil layers (0–20 cm) compared to the deeper layers (20–50 cm) across all sampling locations. This pattern reflects the accumulation of organic matter near the soil surface due to plant litter input, root biomass, and microbial activity. Particularly high C_{tot} and N_{tot} contents were measured at location A8 and B4 in the upper layer, indicating localized zones of enhanced organic matter accumulation. The decline in C and N contents with depth is consistent with reduced organic matter input and increasing mineral soil dominance in deeper horizons. In Transect A, the ditch-associated sampling location (A6) did not show elevated C and N contents compared to surrounding positions, particularly when compared to A8, which exhibited the highest C_{tot} and N_{tot} values within the transect. This contrasts with the expected pattern for ditch-associated sites, where increased moisture availability and enhanced organic matter deposition often promote the accumulation and preservation of organic material. The comparatively lower C and N contents at A6 may indicate site-specific differences in vegetation input, hydrological dynamics, or organic matter turnover. In contrast, the ditch-associated location in Transect B (B4) showed the highest nutrient availability within the transect, with elevated concentrations of C_{tot}, N_{tot}, P-CAL, and exchangeable base cations in the upper soil layer. This pattern is consistent with the expected accumulation of nutrients and organic matter in wetter microsites influenced by periodic water movement and deposition processes.

(VDLUFA 2012).

	<i>pH</i>	<i>elc</i>	<i>P-CAL</i>	<i>K-CAL</i>	<i>K</i>	<i>Na</i>	<i>Mg</i>	<i>Ca</i>	<i>CEC</i>	<i>C_{tot}</i>	<i>N_{tot}</i>	<i>C/N</i>
A2 0 - 20	6,0	76	22	79	2,8	3,5	74,8	320	401	3,0	0,3	12,0
A2 20 - 50	6,3	79	63	88	3,1	3,6	75,0	322	404	2,8	0,2	12,5
A6 0 - 20	5,9	103	110	152	5,2	4,0	72,0	306	387	3,6	0,3	11,9
A6 20 - 50	6,1	70	62	129	4,5	4,0	74,0	302	385	2,2	0,2	12,2
A8 0 - 20	6,2	126	132	294	8,4	2,2	66,1	328	405	5,6	0,4	14,2
A8 20 - 50	6,2	79	43	135	4,9	3,1	70,9	308	387	2,7	0,2	12,7
B1 0 - 20	5,7	115	23	157	5,0	5,1	71,0	284	366	4,1	0,3	13,3
B1 20 - 50	6,2	98	20	111	3,9	6,1	77,7	307	394	3,5	0,2	14,0
B4 0 - 20	5,8	142	81	214	6,4	3,8	79,2	356	445	6,2	0,5	11,5
B4 20 - 50	6,1	77	534	136,8	5,0	3,3	74,6	342	425	2,8	0,2	12,4

Table 2: Chemical Properties of the soil samples

4.2. Meteorological Conditions

The temporal dynamics of precipitation and GWT between April and June 2025 are shown in Figure 27. GWTs, derived from piezometer measurements and modelled using an ARIMAX approach, exhibited a gradual declining trend over the observation period, decreasing from approximately 137.35 m above sea level in early April to around 137.00 m a.s.l. by late June. Superimposed on this overall decline, short-term fluctuations in GWL were observed in response to precipitation events.

Precipitation data obtained from the hydrographic service of the Lower Austrian Provincial Government show a highly episodic pattern, with several distinct rainfall events occurring throughout the study period. Notably, pronounced precipitation peaks were recorded in mid-April, late April (also due to snowmelt), early May, and early June, with the highest single event exceeding 18 mm in early June. These rainfall events were generally followed by short-term increases or stabilization in GWTs, indicating a direct hydrological response of the system. For example, the precipitation events in late April corresponded to a temporary rise in GWL, interrupting the preceding decline. Similarly, the intense rainfall in early June was associated with a brief recovery of GWTs before the downward trend resumed. The reason for the rising level and the highest peak of the GW at the end of April is the snowmelt. Despite these responses, the overall declining trajectory of GWL suggests that evapotranspiration and drainage processes exceeded recharge over the study period. The observed time lag between precipitation peaks and GW response appears to be relatively short, indicating efficient infiltration and hydraulic connectivity between the soil surface and the GW system (eHYD 2026).

Figure 27: Precipitation (mm) and GWT (meters above Adria) over the whole measurement period close to Transect A (Piezometer)

The following Figure 28 shows the temporal development of soil_T and soil_M, presented as mean values per measurement day for transect A and transect B. In both transects,

soil_T exhibited an overall increasing trend over the measurement period from April to June. In transect A, temperatures increased from approximately 8–10 °C in early April to values exceeding 30 °C in late June, with short-term fluctuations, including a pronounced drop in early May caused by consecutive days of rainfall. A similar pattern was observed in transect B, where soil_T also increased steadily over time, with a temporary decrease in early May followed by a continuous rise towards the end of the measurement period.

Soil_M showed a more variable pattern in both transects. In transect A, soil_M values ranged approximately between 10% and 30%, with several fluctuations throughout the measurement period. Higher moisture levels were observed in early May and mid-June, whereas lower values occurred towards the end of June. In transect B, soil_M values were generally higher and exhibited a wider range, reaching peak values above 80% in mid-May. Following this peak, soil_M gradually declined but remained elevated compared to transect A for most of the observation period, before decreasing markedly in late June.

Figure 28: Soil_M [%] and soil_T [°C] mean per measurement day and Transect over the whole experimental period

4.3. Statistical Analysis

4.3.1. Flux calculation

Figure 29 shows an example of the outgoing results of the N₂O Flux calculation for the first measuring day 07.04.2026. For every measuring day and ring, a plot and CSV file like

the following has been calculated. The complete file collection can be found in the dataset attached to this paper.

Figure 29: Output R calculation N₂O fluxes per ring on the first measurement day (07.04.2025)

Descriptive Statistics N₂O Fluxes and Environmental Parameters

Figure 30 illustrates N₂O fluxes in transect A across all sampling dates and measurement points, with bar height representing flux magnitude, colour indicating soil_T, and the line depicting soil_M. The same applies to all subsequent plots in this chapter.

Overall, N₂O fluxes showed pronounced spatial and temporal variability (mean = 12.1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$; standard deviation = 22.8 $\mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$). Fluxes ranged from negative to strongly positive values, with occasional emission peaks exceeding 100 $\mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$, particularly at the beginning of the measurement period (07.04.2025). While most measurement points exhibited predominantly positive fluxes of varying magnitude over time, Mg_a1 consistently showed negative fluxes throughout nearly the entire observation period.

Soil_M fluctuated between approximately 20% and 40% without a clear temporal trend, whereas soil_T increased steadily from April to June, as reflected by the shift from cooler to warmer colour tones.

Figure 30: N₂O Flux [$\mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$] with soil_M [%] and soil_T [°C] of transect A per measurement day

Figure 31 shows N₂O fluxes in transect B across all sampling dates and measurement points. In contrast to transect A, fluxes were almost exclusively positive throughout the observation period, with moderate variability (mean = 19.3 $\mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$; standard deviation = 21.0 $\mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$). Elevated emissions occurred on specific dates, particularly in late April and May, when individual measurement points exceeded 50 $\mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$. Toward June, fluxes became lower and more uniform across the transect. Soil_M remained consistently high, frequently exceeding 60% and occasionally approaching saturation, while soil_T showed a steady seasonal increase.

Figure 31: N₂O Flux [$\mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$] with soil_M [%] and soil_T [°C] of transect B per measurement Day

The comparison of mean N₂O fluxes per measurement point between transect A and transect B shows clear differences in spatial patterns and emission levels (Figure 32 and Figure 33). Therefore, it is important to note that the y-axes of the graphs have different scales. In transect A, mean N₂O fluxes varied strongly between measurement points, including both negative and positive values. Most points exhibited moderate emissions, while one point showed a negative mean flux (Mg_a1). Soil_M remained relatively low and stable (approximately 22–25%), and soil_T showed only minor variation. In contrast, transect B exhibited consistently positive mean N₂O fluxes across all measurement points, with generally higher values than in transect A. Fluxes increased along the transect, reaching maximum values at the final measurement point. This pattern coincided with a strong increase in soil_M from approximately 40% to over 80%, while soil_T was slightly higher and more uniform compared to transect A, but this most probably has to do with the measurement time on a sample date, because transect A (10-12 am) has always been measured before transect B (1-3 pm).

Figure 32: Mean N₂O Flux [μg m⁻² h⁻¹] with mean soil_M [%] and mean soil_T [°C] of transect A per measurement day

Figure 33: Mean N₂O Flux [$\mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$] with mean soil_M [%] and mean soil_T [°C] of transect A per measurement day

Figure 34 provides a detailed temporal resolution of N₂O flux dynamics for each individual measurement point in transect A. The results highlight clear differences in emission patterns between locations: Mg_a1 as only ring in the whole experiment was characterized by persistent N₂O uptake, whereas Mg_a7, Mg_a8, and Mg_a9 exhibited consistently positive emissions with intermittent peaks. Most other points showed moderate fluxes punctuated by short-term increases, particularly during late April and early June (after precipitation events). In contrast to the temporal increase in soil_T, soil_M remained comparatively low (approximately 20–35%) and variable, without a consistent trend. These findings underline the strong small-scale heterogeneity of N₂O fluxes within transect A, both across space and over time.

Transect A: Daily N₂O flux by measurement point (REMARK)

Fixed panel size (3×2 per page). Page 1.

Figure 34: N₂O Flux [$\mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$] with soil_M [%] and soil_T [°C] of transect A per ring

Figure 35 provides a point-specific temporal perspective on N₂O flux dynamics within transect B. While emissions were generally consistent across measurement points, distinct peaks occurred at locations such as Mg_b3 and Mg_b5. Soil_M conditions remained uniformly elevated across all sites, with only moderate temporal fluctuations but consistently higher levels than in transect A.

Figure 35: N₂O Flux [$\mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$] with soil_M [%] and soil_T [°C] of transect B per ring

The comparison of mean daily N₂O fluxes between transect A and transect B reveals clear differences in magnitude and temporal dynamics (Figure 36 and Figure 37). In transect A, N₂O fluxes showed moderate variability over time, with values generally ranging between low and intermediate levels and occasional peaks, particularly in early June. Soil_M remained relatively low and variable (approximately 10–30%), while soil_T increased over the measurement period.

In contrast, transect B exhibited higher mean N₂O fluxes, especially during the early measurement period, with a pronounced peak in early May. Fluxes declined over time but remained consistently positive. Soil_M in transect B was substantially higher than in transect A, ranging from approximately 45% to over 80%, and showed a decreasing trend towards the end of the measurement period. soil_T followed a similar increasing trend as observed in transect A.

Figure 36: Mean N₂O Flux [$\mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$] with mean soi_M [%] and mean soi_T [°C] of transect A per ring

Figure 37: Mean N₂O Flux [$\mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$] with mean soi_M [%] and mean soi_T [°C] of transect B per ring

4.3.2. MI and RMI

The MI analysis revealed clear differences in the strength and significance of relationships between environmental variables and N₂O fluxes across the two transects (Table 3).

Predictor	n	bins	MI	H_Y	RMI	p_value	z_score	sig
TA soil_M	98	6	0,16	1,79	0,09	0,341	0,34	ns
TA soil_T	98	6	0,25	1,79	0,14	0,017	2,49	*
TA GWT	99	6	0,24	1,79	0,13	0,02	2,36	*
TB soil_M	36	10	1,20	2,20	0,54	0,021	2,20	*
TB soil_T	36	6	0,54	1,79	0,30	0,171	1,02	ns
TB GWT	40	6	0,56	1,77	0,32	0,024	2,17	*

Table 3: Results MI and RMI

In transect A, the relationships between environmental drivers and N₂O fluxes were generally weak to moderate. Soil_T (MI = 0.25 nats) and GWT (MI = 0.24 nats) showed statistically significant associations with N₂O fluxes ($p = 0.017$ and $p = 0.020$, respectively), indicating that both variables contributed to explaining flux variability. In contrast, soil_M exhibited a lower MI (MI = 0.16 nats) and was not statistically significant ($p = 0.341$), suggesting a comparatively minor role in controlling N₂O emissions at this site. The normalized results (RMI) support this pattern, showing that soil_T (RMI = 0.14) and GWT (RMI = 0.13) explained a similar proportion of the variability in N₂O flux, whereas soil_M accounted for less than 10% (RMI = 0.09). Overall, these results indicate that in transect A, N₂O flux dynamics were primarily influenced by temperature and GW conditions rather than soil_M.

In transect B, substantially stronger relationships were observed, particularly for soil_M. It exhibited the highest MI (MI = 1.20 nats) and a strong relative contribution (RMI = 0.54), indicating that more than half of the variability in N₂O fluxes was associated with this variable. This relationship was statistically significant ($p = 0.021$) and showed a clear

separation from the null distribution (z-score = 2.20), highlighting soil_M as the dominant controlling factor in this transect. GWT also showed a significant association with N₂O fluxes in transect B (MI = 0.56 nats, RMI = 0.32, p = 0.024), suggesting an additional influence of hydrological conditions. In contrast, soil_T exhibited a moderate MI value (0.54 nats) but was not statistically significant (p = 0.171), indicating that its effect on N₂O flux variability was less consistent.

Across both transects, the RMI followed the same ranking as MI, reflecting the constant entropy of N₂O flux within each dataset. RMI therefore provides an intuitive interpretation of the results by expressing the proportion of flux variability associated with each environmental variable, without altering statistical inference.

4.3.3. GAM

Figure 38 illustrates the partial effects of GWT, soil_T, and soil_M (soil_vH in the figures of this chapter) on N₂O fluxes for both transects. The y-axis represents the estimated contribution of each predictor to the N₂O flux, while shaded areas indicate the associated 95% confidence intervals.

In transect A, soil_T exhibited a significant positive effect on N₂O fluxes (p = 0.039). The partial response curve indicates a monotonic increase in emissions with increasing temperature. In contrast, soil_M showed only a weak and statistically non-significant relationship (p = 0.563), despite a slight positive trend at higher moisture levels. GWT depth displayed a marginal effect (p = 0.059), suggesting a potential influence that did not reach statistical significance.

In transect B, a contrasting pattern was observed. soil_M emerged as the only significant main predictor (p = 0.039), with N₂O fluxes increasing with higher soil_M. soil_T showed no significant effect (p = 0.276), and the corresponding partial effect curve indicated only minor variation across the observed temperature range. The GWT also did not significantly influence N₂O fluxes (p = 0.106), although a weak non-linear tendency was present.

Figure 38: GAM partial effects of the predictors on N₂O Fluxes

The interaction plots in Figure 39 illustrate the combined effects of soil_T, soil_M, and GWT on N₂O fluxes for both transects. The colour gradients represent predicted N₂O flux values, with warmer colours indicating higher emissions and cooler colours indicating lower or negative fluxes.

In Transect A, the interaction surfaces show relatively smooth and gradual gradients across all variable combinations. The response patterns are largely monotonic, indicating that N₂O fluxes increase consistently with increasing soil_T and, to a lesser extent, with soil_M and GWT. The absence of pronounced curvature or localized peaks suggests that interactions between variables are weak and that environmental drivers act mostly independently. This is consistent with the statistical results, where only soil_T resulted significant.

In Transect B, the interaction surfaces exhibit more pronounced structure and variability. Especially in the soil_M–GWT interaction, clear zones of elevated N₂O fluxes emerge under conditions of high soil_M combined with relatively shallow GWTs. This indicates that N₂O emissions are strongly enhanced when both variables jointly promote reduced oxygen availability. In contrast, lower emissions are observed under drier

conditions or deeper GWTs. The curvature of the surfaces suggests that the effect of one variable depends on the level of the other, confirming a true interaction rather than independent effects. The soil_T–soil_M and soil_T–GWT interactions in Transect B show weaker but still noticeable gradients, indicating that soil_T may modulate the effects of hydrological variables, although these interactions were not statistically significant.

Figure 39: GAM interaction effects of combined predictors with N₂O Flux

The statistical results of the GAM analysis are summarized in Table 4. In transect A, only soil_T significantly explained variation in N₂O fluxes, while soil_M, GWT, and all interaction terms remained non-significant. In transect B, soil_M and the interaction between soil_M and GWT were significant predictors, whereas soil_T and the remaining interactions did not show significant effects.

Across both transects, the effective degrees of freedom (edf) provide information on the complexity of the fitted relationship, where values close to one indicate an approximately linear relationship, while higher values suggest increasing non-linearity. The reference degrees of freedom (Ref.df) represent the degrees of freedom used in the statistical testing of each model term. The F-value serves as the test statistic and reflects the strength of the effect of a given predictor on the response variable. The corresponding p-value indicates the probability of observing such an effect under the null hypothesis of no relationship, thereby providing a measure of statistical significance. This suggests that, within the observed environmental ranges, N₂O flux responses can be adequately described by monotonic trends rather than complex non-linear patterns (Lai et al. 2024).

<i>Transect</i>	<i>Predictor/s</i>	<i>edf</i>	<i>Ref,df</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p_value</i>	<i>sig</i>
A	s(soil_T)	1,000016	1,000032	4,407993	0,03853602	*
A	s(soil_M)	1,000182	1,000364	0,337719	0,56272592	ns
A	s(GWT)	1,000012	1,000024	3,662351	0,05879779	ns
A	ti(soil_T,soil_M)	1,000348	1,000695	0,462459	0,49841121	ns
A	ti(soil_T,GWT)	1,000050	1,000100	1,022204	0,31467147	ns
A	ti(soil_M,GWT)	1,000034	1,000680	0,432692	0,51233446	ns
B	s(soil_T)	1,000010	1,000020	1,233300	0,27589011	ns
B	s(soil_M)	1,000034	1,000068	4,678668	0,0389176	*
B	s(GWT)	1,213776	1,402528	1,737963	0,10610198	ns
B	ti(soil_T,soil_M)	1,000046	1,000092	1,632373	0,21150849	ns
B	ti(soil_T,GWT)	1,000028	1,000056	4,072125	0,05293022	ns
B	ti(soil_M,GWT)	1,000367	1,000730	5,912782	0,02141982	*

Table 4: Results GAM

5. Discussion

The N₂O flux patterns observed in this study reflect the strong influence of interacting environmental controls in floodplain ecosystems. The pronounced spatial and temporal variability observed across both transects is therefore consistent with the general understanding of floodplains as heterogeneous biogeochemical hotspots, where small-scale differences in elevation, hydrology, vegetation, land use and soil properties can lead to strongly contrasting GHG fluxes (IPCC 2022).

The magnitude of measured N₂O fluxes in this study was broadly comparable to values reported for Austrian floodplain forests. The study of Schindlbacher et al. 2022 reported mean N₂O fluxes of approximately $6.5 \pm 7.1 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O-N m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ at non-flooded sites, $10.4 \pm 14.3 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O-N m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ at occasionally flooded sites, and $9.4 \pm 10.5 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O-N m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ at frequently flooded sites in the Danube National Park. The mean flux in Transect A ($12.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$) is therefore within the upper range of these Austrian floodplain values, whereas Transect B ($19.3 \mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$) exceeded them, indicating more favourable local conditions for N₂O production. This difference suggests that the Marchegg floodplain site behaves similarly to other temperate floodplain systems, but that local hydrological and soil conditions can create stronger emission hotspots than would be expected from regional averages alone.

5.1. Soil properties and implications for N₂O dynamics

The soil analyses revealed pronounced spatial heterogeneity between and within the investigated transects, particularly regarding texture, nutrient availability, C_{org} content, and hydrological conditions. These differences strongly influenced the observed N₂O dynamics and likely contributed to the contrasting emission patterns between Transect A and Transect B. In general, higher C and N contents were found in the upper soil layer (0–20 cm), reflecting the accumulation of plant-derived organic matter and enhanced microbial activity near the soil surface. Since no C_{inorg} was detected, C_{tot} consisted entirely of C_{org}, underlining the importance of soil organic matter dynamics for microbial N transformations.

Higher N₂O emissions in wetter sections of Transect B were most likely associated with fine-textured and C-rich soils located within former channel structures (ditch). The ditch-associated location B4 exhibited the highest nutrient availability within the transect, including elevated concentrations of C_{tot}, N_{tot}, available phosphorus, and exchangeable base cations. Such soils generally exhibit increased H₂O retention and reduced gas diffusivity, promoting anaerobic microsites and denitrification processes (Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013). Elevated organic C availability may have additionally stimulated microbial activity by providing energy sources for denitrifying microorganisms (Welti 2012). Furthermore, floodplain depressions and ditch structures often accumulate sediments and organic material during inundation events, thereby creating localized hotspots of nutrient cycling and GHG production (Harpenslager et al. 2015).

In contrast, the ditch-associated location in Transect A (A6) did not show similarly elevated C and N contents. Instead, the highest organic matter contents within this transect were observed at A8. This deviation from the expected pattern suggests that local hydrological conditions, vegetation composition, or historical sediment deposition may differ substantially even over short distances. The observed small-scale heterogeneity is characteristic of floodplain ecosystems and can result in highly variable redox conditions and microbial process rates (Vidon et al. 2010).

The occurrence of negative N₂O fluxes in Transect A further suggests that the floodplain soils may temporarily function not only as sources but also as sinks for atmospheric N₂O. Similar observations have been reported in wetland ecosystems under strongly reduced conditions favouring complete denitrification to N₂ (Chapuis-Lardy et al. 2007). Under prolonged anaerobic conditions combined with sufficient carbon availability, N₂O reductase activity may increase, enabling the complete reduction of N₂O to N₂ and thereby promoting net N₂O uptake from the atmosphere (Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013).

Overall, the strong small-scale variability observed between neighbouring measurement points highlights the importance of microtopography and former channel structures in regulating GHG dynamics. These geomorphological features likely function as localized biogeochemical hotspots due to their tendency to accumulate H₂O, nutrients, and organic matter. Comparable hotspot behaviour has been described in

other floodplain ecosystems characterized by strong hydrological heterogeneity and fluctuating redox conditions (Harpenslager et al. 2015; Vidon et al. 2010).

Overall, these findings support H1b₁ and H1c₁ by demonstrating that soil_M conditions, GW influence, and associated redox dynamics strongly affected N₂O flux behaviour. At the same time, the pronounced small-scale heterogeneity between neighbouring sites indicates that local soil properties and microsite conditions modified these environmental controls substantially.

5.1.1. Mg_a1 as a N₂O sink

The first measured ring (Mg_a1) represents an important example of the temporary sink function observed in Transect A. In general, the expected environmental predictors would indicate strongly reduced soil conditions, where denitrification proceeds completely from NO₃⁻ via N₂O to N₂. This typically requires high soil_M, limited oxygen availability, relatively shallow GWT, and sufficient C_{org} as an electron donor for denitrifying microorganisms. Under these conditions, N₂O is not accumulated as an end product but is further reduced to N₂, resulting in negative or very low measured N₂O fluxes (Chapius-Lardy et al. 2007). This interpretation agrees with the general observation that negative N₂O fluxes occurred in Transect A and may indicate that floodplain soils can temporarily act as atmospheric N₂O sinks under reduced conditions (IPCC 2022). However, these sink fluxes should be interpreted cautiously because low or negative chamber fluxes are close to the detection limit and may be sensitive to short-term atmospheric variability and chamber-related uncertainties (Pavelka et al. 2018).

For MG_A1 specifically, the measured predictor conditions only partly support the interpretation of the site acting as a temporary N₂O sink. Although some negative fluxes occurred under relatively moist conditions and hydrological influence (07 April 2025, 6 May 2025), elevated soil moisture and groundwater levels were not consistently associated with the strongest negative fluxes (19 May 2025). This indicates that sink behaviour at MG_A1 cannot be explained by soil moisture or groundwater conditions alone. Nevertheless, periodically reduced oxygen availability in combination with restricted gas diffusivity may still have promoted complete denitrification to N₂ rather than incomplete denitrification with N₂O accumulation during certain measurement

periods. The relatively high CEC measured close to the ring may additionally indicate enhanced nutrient and substrate retention, potentially supporting microbial activity and denitrification processes.

Particularly during June, consistently elevated negative fluxes were measured at MG_A1 despite the prevailing hot and dry conditions. One possible explanation is that dry surface conditions reduced overall microbial N turnover and limited N₂O production through nitrification and denitrification, while small anaerobic microsites may still have persisted in deeper soil layers or organic-rich aggregates. Under such conditions, existing N₂O could have been further reduced to N₂ by active N₂O reductase, resulting in net negative fluxes. In addition, low mineral N availability during dry periods may have further constrained new N₂O formation. Similar temporary sink behaviour under fluctuating environmental conditions has been described for other wetland and floodplain soils, highlighting the complex and non-linear regulation of N₂O consumption processes (Chapuis-Lardy et al. 2007; Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013).

The temporary sink behaviour observed at MG_A1 further emphasizes that the relationships between environmental variables and N₂O fluxes were non-linear and highly context dependent. This partly supports H1b₁ and H1c₁, while also demonstrating that elevated soil_M or shallow GW alone were insufficient to explain all observed flux patterns.

5.2. Meteorological and hydrological controls

Hydrological conditions emerged as the dominant control of N₂O flux dynamics within the investigated floodplain ecosystem. The strongest and most consistent emissions occurred in wetter areas characterized by shallow GWs and elevated soil_M, particularly in Transect B. These conditions likely promoted oxygen depletion and enhanced denitrification activity (Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013; Welti 2012).

The relationship between soil_M and N₂O emissions was clearly non-linear. Highest emissions occurred under moist but not fully saturated conditions, supporting previous findings that peak N₂O production frequently occurs where aerobic and anaerobic microbial pathways coexist simultaneously (Davidson et al. 2000; Kasak et al. 2022).

Under fully saturated conditions, complete denitrification to N_2 may reduce net N_2O emissions.

Contrary to the initial hypothesis, the grazed transect did not exhibit systematically higher emissions despite potential manure inputs and soil disturbance. Instead, the wetter non-grazed transect showed persistently elevated fluxes, suggesting that hydrological conditions outweighed management-related N inputs during the investigated period.

Several factors may explain the comparatively weak grazing effect. First, nutrient deposition by semi-wild Konik horses was likely spatially heterogeneous and may not have coincided with chamber locations. Second, hydrological conditions probably exerted substantially stronger controls on microbial N transformations than grazing-induced nutrient additions. Similar patterns have been reported in restored wetlands and peatlands where GW conditions dominated GHG dynamics (Harpenslager et al. 2015).

When comparing chamber rings with similar soil_M, Transect A exhibited generally higher positive and negative N_2O fluxes than Transect B.

The results emphasize the importance of floodplain hydrology for ecosystem functioning. Seasonal GW fluctuations regulate oxygen availability, nutrient transport, and microbial activity, thereby strongly influencing GHG production. Historical hydromorphological alterations and reduced floodplain connectivity may therefore continue to affect present-day biogeochemical processes in the Marchauen system (Hein et al. 2004).

However, several limitations constrain the interpretation of hydrological controls. GW measurements originated from a single piezometer and may not fully represent local conditions across both transects. In addition, redox conditions were inferred indirectly from soil_M and GW data rather than measured directly. Another important limitation concerns temporal resolution. N_2O emissions are often dominated by short-lived episodic events following flooding, rewetting, or freeze–thaw processes (Groffman et al. 2009). Consequently, the measurement campaign likely captured only part of the annual emission dynamics.

These observations partly confirm H1a₁, H1b₁, and H1c₁, as soil_T, soil_M, and GW conditions all influenced N₂O dynamics, although their effects varied strongly between sites and over time. In contrast, H2a₁ was not supported, since the grazed transect did not exhibit systematically higher emissions than the non-grazed transect. Instead, hydrological conditions appeared to exert stronger controls on N₂O emissions than grazing-related management effects.

5.3. Statistical Analysis

The applied statistical approaches revealed that the relationships between environmental variables and N₂O emissions were complex, non-linear, and highly site-specific. This confirms previous findings that GHG fluxes in wetland ecosystems are difficult to explain using simple linear relationships alone (Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013; Lai et al. 2024; Douglas C. Montgomery 2012; Cover und Thomas 2005)

5.3.1. MI/ RMI and GAM

The MI and RMI analyses indicated that different environmental variables-controlled N₂O emissions in the two transects. In Transect A, soil_T appeared to exert the strongest influence, whereas soil_M and GW conditions were more important in Transect B. These contrasting patterns suggest that the dominant microbial pathways differed between the investigated sites due to differences in hydrological regime and soil properties.

The stronger temperature dependency observed in Transect A may indicate that microbial activity was primarily limited by metabolic constraints rather than oxygen availability. Under comparatively drier conditions, increasing soil_T s likely enhanced microbial respiration and N turnover, thereby stimulating nitrification and denitrification processes. Similar temperature-driven increases in microbial N turnover and N₂O production have also been observed in temperate grassland and agricultural soils (Butterbach-Bahl et al. 2013; Smith et al. 2003).

In contrast, the stronger influence of soil_M in Transect B suggests that hydrological conditions controlled the balance between aerobic and anaerobic microbial pathways. This interpretation is consistent with the observed wetter conditions and higher emissions in this transect. The results therefore support the conceptual understanding

that environmental controls of N₂O emissions are context-dependent and may shift depending on local hydrological conditions.

The GAM analyses further demonstrated that the relationships between environmental variables and N₂O fluxes were strongly non-linear. This is ecologically important because it indicates that floodplain GHG dynamics cannot be adequately represented using linear assumptions. Instead, threshold behaviour and interaction effects appear to play a major role. For example, relatively small increases in soil_M near saturation may trigger disproportionately large changes in oxygen availability and microbial activity. Similar threshold-like responses of N₂O emissions to changing soil_M conditions have frequently been reported for wetland and agricultural soils (Davidson et al. 2000; Linn und Doran 1984). The use of GAMs therefore represents a methodological advantage compared to conventional linear regression approaches because GAMs are capable of capturing flexible and non-monotonic relationships without imposing predefined functional forms (Lai et al. 2024). In heterogeneous systems such as floodplains, this flexibility is particularly important because environmental drivers frequently interact across multiple temporal and spatial scales. Non-linear and scale-dependent behaviour of biogeochemical processes is considered characteristic for heterogeneous wetland ecosystems and often limits the applicability of simple linear modelling approaches (Groffman et al. 2009; McClain et al. 2003)

Nevertheless, the statistical interpretation must be treated cautiously. Although GAMs improve the representation of non-linear patterns, they remain correlative rather than process based models. Consequently, the observed statistical relationships do not necessarily imply direct causal relationships. Similar limitations of correlative environmental models have been highlighted in previous studies investigating wetland greenhouse gas dynamics (Lai et al. 2024). For example, soil_M may act not only as a direct environmental driver but also as an integrative proxy for multiple interacting processes, including oxygen availability, substrate diffusion, microbial activity, and GW connectivity. Furthermore, the relatively limited dataset constrains model robustness and predictive capacity. N₂O emissions are characterized by extremely high temporal variability and often contain substantial stochastic components. Episodic emission pulses following rewetting or short-term hydrological changes are known to contribute disproportionately to annual N₂O budgets (Groffman et al. 2009; Butterbach-Bahl et al.

2013). Under such conditions, statistical relationships may be sensitive to individual emission peaks or short-term environmental fluctuations. This limitation is particularly relevant for machine-learning or highly flexible modelling approaches because overfitting may occur when sample sizes remain moderate. Another important uncertainty concerns temporal autocorrelation. Environmental variables and N₂O emissions were measured repeatedly over time at the same locations, implying that observations were not fully independent. Although GAMs partially accommodate non-linear relationships, temporal dependencies may still influence model behaviour and significance estimates. Future studies should therefore consider mixed-effects or hierarchical modelling approaches to explicitly account for repeated measurements and nested spatial structures.

Despite these limitations, the applied statistical approaches provided important insights into the environmental controls of N₂O dynamics and highlighted the complexity of GHG regulation within floodplain systems. The combination of MI/RMI and GAM analyses proved particularly valuable because it allowed both the identification of dominant environmental controls and the characterization of non-linear system behaviour.

The statistical analyses therefore strongly support H2b₁, indicating that the relationships between environmental variables and N₂O fluxes differed substantially between the two transects. Furthermore, the GAM results provide strong evidence for the non-linear behaviour proposed in H1b₁, particularly regarding the influence of soil_M on N₂O emissions.

5.4. Synthesis

The results of this study demonstrate that N₂O emissions in floodplain ecosystems are governed primarily by hydrological heterogeneity and associated shifts in soil redox conditions. Rather than responding uniformly to land management, the investigated floodplain behaved as a mosaic of spatially distinct biogeochemical environments shaped by GW dynamics, soil properties, and former channel structures.

In particular, wetter and finer-textured former channel areas functioned as localized hotspots of microbial N transformation processes. These findings support the broader

understanding that small-scale hydrological variability can exert disproportionate influence on ecosystem-scale GHG dynamics.

The study further illustrates that floodplain GHG emissions cannot be explained adequately through simple linear relationships or single environmental drivers. Instead, the observed threshold-like responses emphasize the importance of non-linear interactions between hydrology, substrate availability, and microbial activity. These findings have important implications for wetland restoration and climate mitigation. Rewetting and restoration measures may improve biodiversity and C sequestration while simultaneously altering GHG dynamics in complex ways. Effective mitigation strategies therefore require site-specific and process-based understanding of local hydrological and biogeochemical interactions.

5.5. Limitations and uncertainties

Several methodological and conceptual limitations must be considered when interpreting the results of this study:

First, the CM itself introduces uncertainties that may influence flux estimates. Closed chambers alter gas diffusion conditions and may affect temperature, humidity, and pressure within the chamber headspace during measurements (Pavelka et al. 2018). Although precautions were taken to minimize these effects, including exclusion of the initial stabilization phase, small chamber artefacts cannot be excluded completely. This limitation is particularly relevant for low fluxes near the analytical detection limit.

Second, the temporal resolution of the measurements constrains the representativeness of the results. N₂O emissions frequently occur as short-lived pulses associated with hydrological disturbances, precipitation events, or freeze–thaw cycles (Groffman et al. 2009). Because measurements were conducted at discrete time intervals rather than continuously, episodic peak emissions may have been missed. Consequently, annual flux dynamics may differ substantially from the patterns observed during the monitored periods.

Third, the study relied primarily on indirect environmental proxies to infer microbial processes. Soil_M, GWT, and temperature provide important information regarding environmental controls but do not directly measure nitrification, denitrification, or

microbial community composition. Additional measurements of N availability dissolved C_{org} , redox potential, isotopic signatures, or functional microbial genes would therefore substantially improve process-level interpretation.

Fourth, spatial replication remained limited due to logistical and methodological constraints. Floodplain ecosystems are characterized by extreme small-scale heterogeneity, and the investigated transects therefore represent only a subset of the variability present within the Marchauen system. The observed patterns should consequently not be generalized uncritically to the entire floodplain.

Furthermore, only N_2O fluxes were investigated, whereas floodplain GHG balances additionally depend strongly on CO_2 and CH_4 dynamics. Because wetland restoration may simultaneously decrease CO_2 emissions while increasing CH_4 production, ecosystem-scale climate impacts cannot be assessed adequately from N_2O measurements alone. Integrated multi-gas approaches are therefore required to evaluate the net climatic consequences of floodplain restoration measures. However, this was studied in a parallel Masterthesis....so synthesis covers the GHG balance more accurately.

Finally, the interpretation of statistical relationships remains inherently uncertain because environmental drivers in floodplain ecosystems are strongly interconnected. Variables such as soil_M, GW depth, temperature, and substrate availability frequently covary, making it difficult to isolate independent causal mechanisms. The observed relationships should therefore be interpreted primarily as evidence of environmental associations rather than definitive proof of specific microbial pathways.

Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable insights into the environmental regulation of N_2O emissions in a heterogeneous floodplain ecosystem and contributes to the growing understanding of GHG dynamics in restored wetland landscapes.

6. Conclusion

This study investigated N₂O emissions in a floodplain grassland of the Morava River under contrasting hydrological and land-management conditions. The results demonstrated strong spatial and temporal variability in N₂O fluxes and identified hydrological conditions as the dominant environmental control. Higher and more persistent N₂O emissions occurred in wetter areas characterized by shallow GWs, fine-textured soils, and former channel structures. In contrast, the grazed transect showed lower and more variable emissions, including occasional N₂O uptake. Contrary to the initial hypothesis, grazing effects appeared secondary compared to hydrological regulation.

The findings indicate that local GW dynamics and associated shifts in oxygen availability strongly influenced microbial N transformations and denitrification processes. The observed non-linear relationships further suggest that floodplain GHG dynamics are characterized by threshold-like system behaviour rather than simple linear responses. At the same time, the study highlights the substantial uncertainty associated with interpreting GHG dynamics in heterogeneous wetland ecosystems. Spatial heterogeneity, fluctuating redox conditions, and episodic emission events complicate the identification of definitive microbial pathways and limit the representativeness of short-term chamber measurements.

6.1. Outlook and Future Research

The results of this study demonstrate that predicting N₂O emissions in floodplain ecosystems remains challenging because GHG fluxes are governed by highly dynamic interactions between hydrology, soil conditions, and microbial activity. Future research should therefore move beyond purely correlative approaches and focus more strongly on process-based investigations of N transformation pathways.

In particular, direct measurements of redox conditions, N availability, and microbial functional communities are required to better distinguish between nitrification, denitrification, and N₂O consumption processes. Integrating isotopic approaches and

continuous high-frequency monitoring would additionally improve the detection of short-lived emission pulses that are characteristic of wetland systems.

The strong small-scale variability observed in this study further highlights the importance of considering floodplains as spatially heterogeneous systems rather than uniform landscapes. Future restoration and GHG assessments should therefore incorporate microtopography, hydrological connectivity, and former channel structures more explicitly.

Finally, ongoing climate change may substantially alter floodplain GHG dynamics through increasing drought frequency, altered flood regimes, and more extreme hydrological fluctuations. Understanding how these changes influence microbial N cycling will be essential for developing scientifically robust wetland restoration and climate mitigation strategies in the future.

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Declaration of the use of generative AI tools

In the preparation of this master thesis, generative artificial intelligence (AI) tools were used in a supportive and transparent manner in accordance with the BOKU Framework for Dealing with Text-Generating AI Systems.

AI tools, in particular ChatGPT (OpenAI), were used exclusively for assistance in the following areas:

- linguistic revision and improvement of text passages written by the author,
- structuring and organizing content,
- generating preliminary drafts for selected sections (e.g., discussion paragraphs and abstract),
- formulation support for scientific phrasing and clarity,
- translation support between English and German,
- generating graphs and figures based on literature.

All AI-generated content was critically reviewed, revised, and adapted by the author to ensure scientific accuracy, coherence, and consistency with the underlying data and results. No AI-generated content was used without substantial modification and validation. The scientific reasoning, data analysis, interpretation of results, and conclusions presented in this thesis are entirely the independent work of the author.

No AI tools were used for data analysis, statistical modelling, or the generation of scientific results. All analyses (including regression models, MI calculations, and GAM modelling) were performed independently by the author using the statistical software R. The R Codes have partially been written or corrected with the help of AI tools.

Where AI tools contributed to the improvement of language or structure, this support is acknowledged in this declaration in accordance with principles of good scientific practice

List of abbreviations

BOKU	University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna
REWET	REstoration of WETlands to minimise emissions and maximise carbon uptake
WWF	World Wide Fund for Nature
GHG	Greenhouse gases
C	Carbon
N	Nitrogen
N ₂ O	Nitrous Oxide
NO ₃ ⁻	Nitrate
NO ₂ ⁻	Nitrite
NO	Nitric oxide
N ₂	Dinitrogen
NH ₄ ⁺	Ammonium
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CH ₄	Methan
H ₂ O	Water
H ₂ O ₂	hydrogen peroxide
CaCl ₂	calcium chloride
elc	Electrical conductivity
CAL	calcium acetate lactate
P-CAL and K-CAL	Plant-available phosphorus and potassium

CEC	cation exchange capacity
NH ₄ Ac	ammonium acetate
BaCl ₂	barium chloride
AAS	atomic absorption spectroscopy
CNS	elemental analyser
N _{tot}	total nitrogen content
C _{tot}	total carbon content
C _{org}	Organic carbon content
C _{inorg}	Inorganic carbon content
C/N ratio	carbon-to-nitrogen ratio
VDLUFA	Association of German Agricultural Analytic and Research Institutes
CM	Chamber Method
PVC	polyvinyl chloride
MI	Mutual Information
RMI	Relative Mutual Information
GAM	General Additive Model
soil_M, soil_vH	(Volumetric) soil water content, soil moisture
soil_T	soil temperature
GWT	groundwater table, groundwater level
GW	groundwater

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Appendix

All the protocols, Trace Gas Analyzer Data Output, R-Codes and further Tables and Calculations used for this study can be found in the corresponding data record submitted with this thesis.